

PROFESSIONAL
ENGLISH FOR COMMERCE &
MANAGEMENT - II

TAMIL NADU STATE COUNCIL FOR HIGHER EDUCATION
(TANSCHÉ)

Unit -1 – Communicative Competencies

1. Listening

Pre- task:

Learn some specific business and economics vocabulary!

The lists below are a good general starting point for building your business and economics vocabulary:

Nouns (general)			
Acquisition	Goods	merchandise	restructure
Agenda	Growth	merger	risk
Brand	Incentive	niche	segment
Commodity	Industry	output	services
Correction	Inventory	projection	stock
Deadline	Logistics	prospectus	strategy
Expansion	Manufacturing	report	target

Here is a list of some more particular verbs:

Advertise	Develop	invest	recruit
Allocate	Distribute	invoice	refund
Authorise	Diversify	maintain	report
Calculate	Employ	manage	respond
Compete	Establish	negotiate	run
Control	Estimate	produce	streamline
Delegate	Fund	promote	supply
Deliver	Improve	purchase	target

The list below has some useful adjectives. Note that many of these can also be commonly used as adverbs or turned into adverbs (*).

affordable*	efficient*	offshore	regional*
annual*	financial*	operating	regulatory
commercial*	Fiscal	primary*	retail
competitive*	Fixed	productive*	secondary
Core	holistic*	profitable*	solvent
depreciable*	international*	prosperous*	strategic*
domestic*	logistical*	publicly*	underperforming
economic*	Niche	quarterly*	volatile

Word families

Using different word forms of a particular 'root' word can also give your expression more variety:

Noun	Verb	Adjective	Adverb
product, production	Produce	productive	productively
competitor, Competition	compete (+ preposition)	competitive	competitively
Profit	profit (+ preposition)	profitable	profitably

If you are not sure of the spelling for a particular word form, consult a dictionary like Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary which details various derivatives of a word under the 'Browse List' heading.

Collocations

Developing a good vocabulary is not just about learning words in isolation. Rather, think about groups of words that often go together in print and/or speech. These combinations, known as collocations, are well known and often used by native speakers. In contrast, other combinations may sound unnatural. Some examples below illustrate this:

Natural expression	Unnatural expression
human resources	people resources
customer or client service	buyer service
sales team	sales squad

Nouns

brand/make	cost/expense	overhead/operating cost
cash/currency	customer/client	revenue/return
competitor/rival	employees/workforce	seller/vendor
Verbs		
allocate/assign	forecast/predict	promote/encourage
calculate/determine	observe/detect	replicate/reproduce
employ/appoint	produce/manufacture	suggest/nominate
Adjectives		
comprehensive/wide-Ranging	dominant/prevaling	profitable/lucrative
conditional/qualified	financial/monetary	thriving/successful
distinctive/characteristic	fixed/set	unified/integrated

Note too that some words may sound similar or indeed have similar meanings however, it is important you choose exactly the right word for your purpose. That is, ask yourself are you talking about a 'recession' or a 'depression', the 'internet' or 'intranet' or a 'monopoly', or 'duopoly'? If in any doubt, consult a dictionary!

Antonyms

When you are dealing with terms that have a specific opposite (antonym) be careful because if you choose the wrong option the logic (coherence) of your work will suffer. In fact, often the opposite looks and/or sounds somewhat similar to the original word so be careful with proofreading! Some common opposites for business contexts include:

Nouns		
buyer/seller	inflation/deflation	outlay/income
employer/employees	lender/borrower	supply/demand
goods/services	mentor/mentee	wholesaler/retailer

Verbs

buy/sell	diversify/narrow	own/rent
display/hide	lend/borrow	rise/fall

Adjectives

fixed/variable	nominal/actual	retrospective/prospective
gross/net	probable/unlikely	standard/custom made
intangible/tangible	public/private	wholesale/retail

Positive/Negative

Nouns	asset/liability	boom/bust	profit/loss
Adjectives	affordable/Prohibitive	In vogue/obsolete	viable/impossible
Verbs	employ/terminate	promote/discourage	fulfill/breach

I. Primary Text 1:

How Blockchain can transform India? – Jaspreet Bindra- TEDxChennai:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8fbhI1qVj0c>

I. After listening to the above video answer the following questions.

1. What are the challenges that a hacker may face in the blockchain?
2. Mention the resources that are needed to maintain a Blockchain!
3. What are the contradictory views expressed by the finance minister of India on crypto currency and Blockchain?
4. Why do farmers kill themselves as per the video?
5. How can blockchain help farmers?
6. How did the internet emerge as a problem solver?
7. Block chain is able to solve the issues which the internet has failed to solve. Identify the problem mentioned in the video.

II. Add prefixes to the following words!

- a) Security b) smart c) own d) trust e) Power

III. Fill in the blanks

1. _____ invented the concept of block chain.
2. The heart of blockchain technology is _____ universal ledger _____.
3. _____ Distributed trust _____ is the soul of the block chain.
4. Moresis _____ country is called as Ethereum Island
5. Agriculture in India has _____ 16 _____ percent of GDP.
6. _____ Andra Pradesh _____ state has already started using Block chains in Agriculture.

7. _____ banks _____ is adopting block chains.

IV. Match the Following

1. **Chit Funds** - a digital or virtual currency that is secured by cryptography.
2. **Ledger** - a growing list of records that are linked using cryptography
3. **Crypto currency** - record used to store bookkeeping entries for balance-sheet
4. **Block chain**- a saving and credit product which bears a pre-determined value of a fixed period.

Primary Text 2

The Power of an Entrepreneurial Mindset- Bill Roche- TEDxLangleyED:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ihs4VFZWwn4>

I. Answer the following questions in connection with the above video:

1. How important it is to nurture the entrepreneurial mindset amidst the young people?
2. "In it to Win It"- Explain it with regard to the topic entrepreneurial mindset!
3. Does your society lack an entrepreneurial mindset? State reasons for the lacking!
4. List out some of the young entrepreneurs whom you know? Who inspired you the most among them? Why?
5. How can an education system of a country support and prepare the young minds towards entrepreneurship?

6. List out the other Key features that will really help the entrepreneurs be successful in businesses, besides Bill Roche's three strategies!
7. What do you think is the most important skill a person should obtain to solve problems in the business environment, Critical or Creative?
8. How trade shows would help the entrepreneurs flourish in their businesses?

II. Find out the Etymology of the following words used by the Expert in the video!

- | | |
|------------------|---------------|
| 1. Entrepreneur- | 6. Marketing- |
| 2. Profit - | 7. Strategy - |
| 3. Creativity - | 8. Data - |
| 4. Survey - | 9. Consensus- |
| 5. Critical - | 10. Trade - |

III. Identify the kind of sentences (Declarative, Interrogative, Imperative, Exclamatory, Negative sentence, Conditional etc.) given below that are taken from the Video Presentation!

1. What color would you like? _____
2. Mimie was not a strong academic student _____
3. What can I make a difference in the world by creating a product?

4. Give it a try! _____
5. If you take risks, you will succeed! _____

IV. Discover the meanings for the following idioms (Used by the Expert) in business context! Write sentences by using them!

1. Head on -
2. On Board-
3. Move Forward-
4. Hanging up-
5. Roll up-

V. Prepare a Pictorial Representation (Bar/ Pie Charts/ Graph) that highlights the emergence of the Young Entrepreneurs of India in the last Five Years! Attempt a speech presentation on the above work! (Specific focus on the Content and Choice of Diction/ Business

Registers)

VI. Identify singular or plural from the following words!

- 1. Data -
- 2. Fact -
- 3. Consensus -
- 4. Strategy -
- 5. Prototype-

VII. Identify & arrange the video speech by Bill Roche into various sub-topics!

VIII. Learn Some Business Buzz given below and list out the Business words that you know!

- | | |
|-------------------------|-----------|
| 1. Deep Dive | 7. _____ |
| 2. Corporate Energy | 8. _____ |
| 3. Bleeding edge | 9. _____ |
| 4. Move the Needle | 10. _____ |
| 5. Low hanging fruit | 11. _____ |
| 6. Think out of the box | 12. _____ |

2. Speaking

Think and reflect:

1. What is banking?
2. How do banks help ordinary people?
3. What are the changes that have recently taken place in the banking sector?

I. Primary Text -1

Read the following comprehension passage!

Banking and banks are very important for the functioning of the modern world. Without banks the way we use money would not work. Banks enable people to save money, borrow money and to pay for things with ease and security.

Each country in the world has its own well known banks that have branches in nearly every city so that they are convenient for people to use. People often have to visit the local branch of the bank when they want certain services. There are also some very big multinational banks that have branches in most countries in the world.

As well as the local branches that are in most cities, each bank will also have a head office. This is where all central tasks are performed that let the local branches function. The people that work in the branches will be the bank manager, the person in charge, and various tellers who work behind the bank counter and help the customers. There will also likely be security guards to protect the money, workers and customers.

Most customers will just need to see the tellers when they go to the bank if they are paying money into their account as either cash or a check. However, they might need to see the bank manager if they want to open an account or if they have become overdraw, when they have spent more money than there was in the account. Also, if they want to borrow money and get a loan the person will need to see the bank manager who will have to approve it.

As well as being able to use cash or checks to pay for things, banks also offer their customers the more convenient methods of using either a debit card or credit card. These methods are very convenient as you just need to carry a small plastic card to be able to pay for anything. When paying with plastic you will need to either sign a receipt or enter a PIN number to conform the purchase and that you are authorized to use the card.

<https://www.excellentesl4u.com/esl-banking-reading-comprehension.html>

II. a. Vocabulary

1. **Credit card** - A small plastic card that can be used to buy items. The balance has to be paid also in instalment at the end of the month. (*noun*)
2. **Passbook** - A book containing a record of all the account transactions. (*noun*)
3. **Transaction** - Any situation where money is deposited or withdrawn from an account.
4. **Withdrawal** - To take money out of one's own account.
5. **PIN number** - A four digit number used to access ATM machines.
6. **Loan** - Borrowed money that is received now but needs to be paid back, often monthly, with interest added.
7. **Cash** - Money in the form of notes or coins.

b. List out the words/ terms/ Jargon associated with banking!

- | | |
|----------|-----------|
| 1. _____ | 6. _____ |
| 2. _____ | 7. _____ |
| 3. _____ | 8. _____ |
| 4. _____ | 9. _____ |
| 5. _____ | 10. _____ |

III. Answer the following questions based on the reading comprehension:

1. According to the text, what do banks enable people to do?
2. What is the purpose of the head office of a bank?
3. What do bank tellers do?

4. What happens when a bank customer spends more money than they have in their account?
5. Which of the following methods is more convenient when paying for something other than using a cheque?

IV. Divide the students into small groups and speak on the following topic!

1. Money Transaction Methods
2. Is Online Banking safe?
3. Advantages and disadvantages of Credit cards
4. Offers rendered by banks for the Formers, Women Entrepreneurs & small businesses.
5. PPF and Mutual Funds- Bank Saving Schemes

References:

1. <https://www.excellentesl4u.com/esl-banking-reading-comprehension.html>
2. <https://www.excellentesl4u.com/esl-banking-vocabulary.html>

Primary Text - 2

1. The rarest commodity is leadership without ego: Bob Davis- TEDxESCP
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UQrPVMcgJJk>

Supplementary Texts:

1. How to be a leader- The 7 Great Leadership Traits:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2IEp4TVpxgA&t=93s>
2. 6 types of leadership styles- Management Challenges & Examples:
<http://training-gems.com/types-leadership-styles-management-challenges-examples/>

(The students can be divided into groups to do the following activities)

I. Answer the following questions!

1. Why does the speaker encourage us to read the book "Up the Organization" by Robert Townsend? What is the book all about?

2. What do you know about the expert Bob Davis?
3. What is the difference between Managing and Leading People in Business?
4. What are the three things that one can control in life?
5. Whom does Bob Davis refer to as his favourite leader? Why?
6. Suggest an alternate topic to the speech presentation by Bob Davis!

II. Inferences versus Facts.

Discuss in group whether each of the following statements is an inference or a verifiable fact based on observation and one student from each group can represent the group's idea!

1. The boss is a "swinger".
2. Employees over 60 are inefficient.
3. Leadership is the rarest commodity on the earth
4. All CEOs are "undercover bosses".
5. Power annihilates the leadership.
6. Leadership is innate.
7. Autocratic leadership helps the employees to be more productive.

III. Battle it! – Learning through games (Building Vocabulary and sentence structure)

1. Every group can pick out some of the dictions/ idioms/ terms/ concepts/ Acronyms from the Primary and supplementary video texts and challenge the other groups to say meanings/ talk about it for a minute. All groups can take a turn to challenge the other groups. The group that gets maximum points will be declared as the winner of the game.

II. Discuss the following questions/ topics in groups!

2. Compassion+ altruism+ ego-less state= Leadership
3. How vision and creativity contribute to successful leadership?
4. Integrity is the key to genuine leadership.

3. Reading

I. Read the following Comprehension Passage:

The United States and all other modern industrial economies experience significant swings in economic activity. In some years, most industries are booming and unemployment is low; in other years, most industries are operating well below capacity and unemployment is high. Periods of economic prosperity are typically called expansions or booms; periods of economic decline are called recessions or depressions. The combination of expansions and recessions, the ebb and flow of economic activity, is called the business cycle. Business cycles as we know them today were codified and analyzed by Arthur Burns and Wesley Mitchell in their 1946 book *Measuring Business Cycles*. One of the key insights of Burns and Mitchell's was that many economic indicators move together.

During an expansion, not only does output rise, but also employment rises and unemployment falls. New construction also typically increases, and inflation may rise if the expansion is particularly brisk. Conversely, during a recession, the output of goods and services declines, employment falls, and unemployment rises; new construction also declines. In the era before World War II, prices also typically fell during a recession (i.e., inflation was negative); since the 1950s prices have continued to rise during downturns, though more slowly than during expansions (i.e., the rate of inflation falls). Burns and Mitchell defined a recession as a period when a broad range of economic indicators falls for a sustained period, roughly for an year. Just as there is no regularity in the timing of business cycles, there is no reason why cycles have to occur at all.

The prevailing view among economists is that there is a level of economic activity, often referred to as full employment, at which the economy could stay forever. Full employment refers to a level of production in which all the inputs to the production process are being used, but not so intensively that they wear out, break down, or insist on higher wages and more vacations. When the economy is at full employment, inflation tends to remain constant; only if output moves above or below normal does the rate of inflation systematically tend to rise or fall. If nothing disturbs the economy, the full-employment level of output, which naturally tends to grow as the population increases and new technologies are discovered, can be maintained forever. There is no reason why a time of full employment has to give way to either an inflationary boom or a recession.

Business cycles do occur, however, because disturbances to the economy of one sort or another push the economy above or below full employment. Inflationary booms can be generated by surges in private or public spending. For example, if the government spends a lot to fight a war but does not raise taxes, the increased demand will cause not only an increase in the output of war

materiel, but also an increase in the take-home pay of defense workers. The output of all the goods and services that these workers want to buy with their wages will also increase, and total production may surge above its normal, comfortable level. Similarly, a wave of optimism that causes consumers to spend more than usual and firms to build new factories may cause the economy to expand more rapidly than normal. Recessions or depressions can be caused by these same forces working in reverse. A substantial cut in government spending or a wave of pessimism among consumers and firms may cause the output of all types of goods to fall.

Another possible cause of recessions and booms is monetary policy. The Federal Reserve System strongly influences the size and growth rate of the money stock, and thus the level of interest rates in the economy. Interest rates, in turn, are a crucial determinant of how much firms and consumers want to spend. A firm faced with high interest rates may decide to postpone building a new factory because the cost of borrowing is so high. Conversely, a consumer may be lured into buying a new home if interest rates are low and mortgage payments are therefore more affordable. Thus, by raising or lowering interest rates, the Federal Reserve is able to generate recessions or booms. This description of what causes business cycles reflects the Keynesian or new Keynesian view that cycles are the result of nominal rigidities. Only when prices and inflationary expectations are not fully flexible can fluctuations in overall demand cause large swings in real output. An alternative view, referred to as the new classical framework, holds that modern industrial economies are quite flexible. As a result, a change in spending does not necessarily affect real output and employment. For example, in the new classical view a change in the stock of money will change only prices; it will have no effect on real interest rates and thus on people's willingness to invest. In this alternative framework, business cycles are largely the result of disturbances in productivity and tastes, not of changes in aggregate demand.

The empirical evidence is strongly on the side of the view that deviations from full employment are often the result of spending shocks. Monetary policy, in particular, appears to have played a crucial role in causing business cycles in the United States since World War II. For example, the severe recessions of both the early 1970s and the early 1980s were directly attributable to decisions by the Federal Reserve to raise interest rates. On the expansionary side, the inflationary booms of the mid-1960s and the late 1970s were both at least partly due to monetary ease and low interest rates. The role of money in causing business cycles is even stronger if one considers the era before World War II. Many of the worst prewar depressions, including the recessions of 1908, 1921, and the Great Depression of the 1930s, were to a large extent the result of monetary contraction and high real interest rates. In this earlier era, however, most monetary swings were engendered not by deliberate monetary policy but by financial panics, policy mistakes, and international monetary developments.

<https://aspirantszone.com/reading-comprehension-economy-based-bank-po/>

1. Which of the following is TRUE in the context of the passage?
 - a) Boom in an economy can be caused by cutting down the government expenditure.
 - b) Central bank is solely responsible to bring a boom/ recession in the economy by changing the interest rates.
 - c) Full employment level of output can be maintained in an economy forever.
 - d) Post World War II the inflation rates fell but didn't become negative as

compared to pre-World War II.

- A) Both b) and c)
- B) Both b) and d)
- C) Both c) and d)
- D) Only b)

2. In a perfect scenario of Full employment what can cause a business cycle to occur?
 - a) A wave of optimism among consumers and producers.
 - b) When the government's expenditure exceeds its income.
 - c) When government's income exceeds its expenditure or reduction in government spending.
 - d) Pessimism among government officials.
 - A) All of these
 - B) Both a) and b)
 - C) Both b) and c)
 - D) All a), b) and c)
 - E) Only b)

3. Prewar depressions, including the one of 1908, 1921 and great depression of 1930s were the result of which phenomena?
 - A) Increase in money supply
 - B) decrease in money supply
 - C) Rise in real interest rates.
 - D) both A) and B)
 - E) both B) and C)

4. What theory does the alternative view or classical view hold?
 - A) Modern economies are rigid.
 - B) Change in spending does not necessarily change output and employment.
 - C) both A) and B)
 - D) business cycles are the result of changes in aggregate demand
 - E) both B) and D)

5. How does the monetary policy affects the spending habits of the public?
 - A) It influences the size and growth rate of money stock and eventually the rates of interests.
 - B) In case of high interests, a firm may postpone its decision to build a factory.
 - C) Monetary policy stances adopted by the central bank can throw an economy into expansion or depression.
 - D) Monetary policy affects the magnitude of the money supply in the economy.
 - E) All of these.

6. In an economy, where interest rates are low what could be the possible outcome?
 - A) Such an economy reflects a period of depression.
 - B) Public will be willing to borrow more as the cost of money rises.
 - C) Banks will be willing to lend more.
 - D) The monthly repayments of mortgage will decrease.

7. What can we infer from the paragraph regarding the full employment situation?

- A) Full employment is an economic situation of optimal utilization of all resources available.
- B) Full employment is an economic situation in which all available resources are being used in the most efficient way that they wear out, break down, or insist on higher wages and more vacations.
- C) Full employment is the situation of employment provided to all the skilled labour.
- D) all of these.
8. What was the main cause of business cycles in the US post world war II?
- A) Changes in public and private expenditure.
- B) Changes in demand pattern
- C) Monetary policy
- D) disturbances in the economy.
9. What can be the suitable title of the passage?
- A) Monetary policy
- B) business cycles
- C) Keynesian view and alternative view on business cycles.
- D) Effects of business cycles on unemployment.
10. What is recession according to Burns and Mitchell?
- A) When a broad range of economic indicators falls for a short period.
- B) When a broad range of economic indicators falls for a very long period may be 1 year.
- C) When a broad range of economic indicators falls for a unrelenting period of time like 6 months.
- D) All of these.

II. Answer the following questions in connection with the passage!

1. What is business cycle?
2. How do economic indicators play an important role in expansion and recession?
3. How is the Federal Reserve able to generate recessions or booms?
4. What were the effects of Monetary Policy on the United States of America?
5. What are the reasons for pre-war depressions?

III. Refer the following Glossary /words/phrases!

- **Full employment-** is an economic situation in which all available not only, but also the land, capital and organization resources are being used in the most efficient way possible. Full employment embodies the highest amount of skilled and unskilled labour that can be employed within an economy at any given time.
- **Business cycle** – Business cycles are identified as having four distinct phases: expansion, peak, contraction, and trough. Business cycles are identified as having four distinct phases: expansion, peak, contraction, and trough.

Contraction -A period of economic decline or negative growth.

Peak - The highest value reached by some quantity in a time period.

Trough - The lowest turning point of a business cycle.

Expansion - The act or process of expanding.

- **Monetary policy** – The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) uses the monetary policy to manage liquidity or money supply in a manner that balances inflation and at the same time aids growth. It affects the money supply in the economy by changing the interest rates in turn affecting the demand of products which is responsible for inflation/deflation.

Primary Text – 2

Federal efforts to aid minority businesses began in the 1960's when the Small Business Administration (SBA) began making federally guaranteed loans and government-sponsored management and technical assistance available to minority business enterprises. While this program enabled many minority entrepreneurs to form new businesses, the results were disappointing, since managerial inexperience, unfavorable locations, and capital shortages led to high failure rates. Even 15 years after the program was implemented, minority business receipts were not quite two percent of the national economy's total receipts. Recently federal policymakers have adopted an approach intended to accelerate development of the minority business sector by moving away from directly aiding small minority enterprises and toward supporting larger, growth-oriented minority firms through intermediary companies. In this approach, large corporations participate in the development of successful and stable minority businesses by making use of government-sponsored venture capital. The capital is used by a participating company to establish a Minority Enterprise Small Business Investment Company or MESBIC. The MESBIC then provides capital and guidance to minority businesses that have potential to become future suppliers or customers of the sponsoring company.

MESBIC's are the result of the belief that providing established firms with easier access to relevant management techniques and more job-specific experience, as well as substantial amounts of capital, gives those firms a greater opportunity to develop sound business foundations than does simply making general management experience and small amounts of capital available. Further, since potential markets for the minority businesses already exist through the sponsoring companies, the minority businesses face considerably less risk in

terms of location and market fluctuation. Following early financial and operating problems, sponsoring corporations began to capitalize MESBIC's far above the legal minimum of \$500,000 in order to generate sufficient income and to sustain the quality of management needed. MESBIC's are now emerging as increasingly important financing sources for minority enterprises.

Ironically, MESBIC staff, which usually consist of Hispanic and Black professionals, tend to approach investments in minority firms more pragmatically than do many MESBIC directors, who are usually senior managers from sponsoring corporations. The latter often still think mainly in terms of the "social responsibility approach" and thus seem to prefer deals that are riskier and less attractive than normal investment criteria would warrant. Such differences in viewpoint have produced uneasiness among many minority staff members, who feel that minority entrepreneurs and businesses should be judged by established business considerations. These staff members believe their point of view is closer to the original philosophy of MESBIC's and they are concerned that, unless a more prudent course is followed, MESBIC directors may revert to policies likely to re-create the disappointing results of the original SBA approach.

<https://www.bms.co.in/reading-comprehension-passage-questions-11th-oct13/>

I. Based on the Passage, answer the following questions:

1. Which of the following best states the central idea of the passage?

- (A) The use of MESBIC's for aiding minority entrepreneurs seems to have greater potential for success than does the original SBA approach.
- (B) There is a crucial difference in point of view between the staff and directors of some MESBIC's.
- (C) After initial problems with management and marketing, minority businesses have begun to expand at a steady rate.
- (D) Minority entrepreneurs wishing to form new businesses now have several equally successful federal programs on which to rely.
- (E) For the first time since 1960, large corporations are making significant contributions to the development of minority businesses

2. According to the passage, the MESBIC approach differs from the SBA approach in that MESBIC's

- (A) Seek federal contracts to provide markets for minority businesses
- (B) Encourage minority businesses to provide markets for other minority businesses
- (C) Attempt to maintain a specified rate of growth in the minority business sector
- (D) Rely on the participation of large corporations to finance minority businesses
- (E) Select minority businesses on the basis of their location

3. Which of the following does the author cite to support the conclusion that the results of the SBA program were disappointing?

- (A) The small number of new minority enterprises formed as a result of the program
- (B) The small number of minority enterprises that took advantage of the management and technical assistance offered under the program
- (C) The small percentage of the nation's business receipts earned by minority enterprises following the programs, implementation.
- (D) The small percentage of recipient minority enterprises that were able to repay federally guaranteed loans made under the program
- (E) The small number of minority enterprises that chose to participate in the program

4. Which of the following statements about the SBA program can be inferred from the passage?

- (A) The maximum term for loans made to recipient businesses was 15 years.
- (B) Business loans were considered to be more useful to recipient businesses than was management and technical assistance.
- (C) The anticipated failure rate for recipient businesses was significantly lower than the rate that actually resulted.
- (D) Recipient businesses were encouraged to relocate to areas more favorable for business development.
- (E) The capitalization needs of recipient businesses were assessed and then provided for adequately

5. The author's primary objective in the passage is to

- (A) Disprove the view that federal efforts to aid minority businesses have been ineffective
- (B) Explain how federal efforts to aid minority businesses have changed since the 1960's
- (C) Establish a direct link between the federal efforts to aid minority businesses made before the 1960's and those made in the 1980's
- (D) Analyze the basis for the belief that job-specific experience is more useful to minority businesses than is general management experience
- (E) Argue that the "social responsibility approach" to aiding minority businesses is superior to any other approach

II. Elaborate the Acronym given below!

- 1. SBA -
- 2. ROI -
- 3. GDP -

- 4. AGM -
- 5. MESBIC -
- 6. P/E -
- 7. P&L -
- 8. KPIs -

4. Writing

Pre-task:

1. What is a summary?
2. When do we write a summary?
3. How to write a summary?

The following are some of the list of author tags used in summary writing:

Says	Explains	Comments
Persuades	Suggests	Understands
Argues	Reminds	Helps us understand
Elucidates	Presents	Intimates
Concludes	Presents the idea	Creates the impression
Criticizes	Defines	Highlights
Concedes	Shows	States
Thinks	Admits	Lists
Notes	Analyzes	Disagrees
Observes	Points out	Emphasizes
Discusses	Identifies	Implies
Insists	Responds	Shows
Proves	Rejects	Suggests

Template of Summary:

Part of Summary	Contents

Part of Summary	Contents
Introduction Sentence	In "My Favorite Shoe," Treyvon Jones explains (insert main idea).
Supporting Arguments	Jones supports this view by pointing out (insert author's supporting arguments).
Final Point	In addition, (insert author's overarching argument and point).

<https://owlcation.com/academia/How-to-Write-a-Summary>

I. Read the following article carefully!

Professionalism is defined by a person's work ethics rather than the pay check, role and title!

A few years ago, a person was termed to be professional based on his pay check and financial independence including the qualifications he has, but now even during this pandemic majority of the companies seek employees with strong moral values, resourceful attitude, being transformative, having positive relationship with their team and not taking credit of their work. Building principled work ethics at the office will help people perceive us in a positive light and propel us ahead in our career. So here comes the major role of "WORK ETHICS" – which is the root where people assess our values, behaviour and our strength.

What does the term Work Ethic mean? It is the ability to maintain proper moral values, standards of behaviour within the professional environment. The final output of this process will be the attitude that shapes a person to perform his individual duties with motivation and loyalty standards.

From the olden days any workplace has people from diverse cultures, backgrounds, belief and value systems. In order to stabilize this, the guidelines provided by the company or the institution will be a support system to maintain the decorum and achieve the objective of the company. *"To make it to the TOP you have to outwork everyone else"*. Talent, Network, Qualifications, certifications can help a person to achieve his dreams, no but these alone won't do it. One needs to believe and abide standards to mould his attitude and character.

******For instance, Amazon CEO Jeff Bezos always had a relentless work ethic. One of his previous classmates told Wired that once Bezos made it clear that he intended to be high school valedictorian, "everyone else understood they were working for second place." The early days at Amazon were characterized by working 12-hour days, seven days a week, and being up

until 3 a.m. to get books shipped. Now that Amazon's a giant, Bezos personally emails teams about customer service issues and has them present directly to him about how they're going to solve them, according to an excerpt from Brad Stone's book, *The Everything Store*.**

In any top-rated businesses, Ethics plays a major role more than monetary benefit. We create examples to the next generation leaders on how to do business (Kick start business) in return how to build the network with uniform code of conduct and make profit. *Still thinking, is it necessary to focus on Ethical part of the profession?* Here are the points on why Work Ethics is important for an organization to go up the ladder or to maintain the standard.

- Having a Code of Ethics provides a Moral compass during the hard times

This Pandemic has taught a lesson on many things including the professional part of our life. During the initial stages of the lockdown, having an SOP for every operation would have been a great tool for many organizations to make quick decisions on planning the work and other mandatory actions.

- Ethics in Workplace support employee Growth and provide meaning to the activity they carry
By maintaining a set of standard frameworks, employees will have the accountability in all the activities they do. This will be a journal to track their performance and take the next step for their betterment.
- Clear business Ethics promote a Strong public Image and Goodwill
This is so true that many would have heard from our friends or gone through articles which says that this is an Employee friendly organization.

According to the press release by The Economic times about The Best companies to work in India for the year 2020, companies like DHL, HP, Croma, Indian Oil, Tech Mahindra, ACT, Blue Dart and so on; have been awarded as the companies which have a Great place to work. This

achievement is possible because they have followed a specific code of Conduct across their branches.

SOP'S and firm's performance are very much related to each other. There could be numerous reasons for a person to be unethical. Besides a person being unethical it could also affect the organizations and individual growth for various reasons.

- Lack of work ethics can lead to lack of trust among the workers and also between various levels of the organization
- Secondly, lack of work ethics affects the credibility among stakeholders
- Third, being one of the important factors for a great place to work is the Environment both within and outside the organization.
- Furthermore, unethical firms invite the Government's attention which would lead to impose penalties, fines, cancellations of licences and so on.

Hence, these individual differences can be maintained through a strong principle followed by the organization. Ethics determines the firm's longevity and its relationship with workers, business partners, stakeholders and the Society. Regardless in what country a firm is or its culture, there are always vital values such as respect, honesty, integrity, tolerance and trust that should prevail for the well-being of everyone involved with the firm.

II. Identify the Introduction sentence, supporting arguments and final point from the above article!

III. Pick out the key words/ terms or phrases from the above articles that would help you to write a Summary!

IV. Draft the summary of the above article by using the Key terms that you have collected!

Primary Text – 2

I. Read the following passage carefully!

A product profile is a general description of a product. Based on the style of presentation, the amount of detail it contains can vary. The product profile details what the product is and how it will appeal to the consumer. The objective is to determine what makes the product attractive to the consumer. This is an important analysis that will help in the marketing of the product.

Mass marketing is a technical term that refers to the selling of a product on a large scale. It involves products that are produced in large quantities. There may be minor differences in localized markets. The mass marketing strategy ignores these. Mass marketing appeals to the whole market with a single offer or strategy. This is done by broadcasting a message that will reach the largest number of consumers possible.

Mass marketing uses the mass media to get their message across. Radio, television and newspapers are the usual vehicles employed. With the advent of social media, strategies are now also devised to take advantage of this new avenue. Exposure to a product is maximized by reaching the largest audience possible. This often directly correlates to a larger number of sales.

Mass marketing focuses on high sales and low prices. This is just the opposite of Niche marketing. Niche marketing targets a very specific segment of the market. It involves specialized services or goods with few or no competitors.

Mass marketing came into existence in the 1920s when mass radio came into use. The mass radio, broadcasting to huge audiences nationwide gave corporations an opportunity to appeal to a wide variety of potential customers. Before this, the strategy of marketing was what may be called variety marketing. In this strategy, different methods were used to appeal to different sections of society most often according to geographical location. In order to appeal to and persuade a wide audience, this had to change. Over the years, mass marketing has developed into a world-wide multi-billion dollar industry.

Things which are perceived as necessary or essential are subjected to mass marketing. To further increase profits, these products are often touted as durable goods when oftentimes they are made of substandard materials. This affects the longevity of the product. This practice of planned obsolescence ensures future sales opportunities by preventing the market from becoming saturated with high-quality, long-lasting goods.

One of the biggest benefits of mass marketing is that the target audience is broad. This translates to a higher number of successful sales. Drop in sales in some areas may be offset by sales in other areas. This helps overcome potential losses. Another positive factor is that production costs are lowered by mass production. Marketing research and advertising costs too are lowered. Mass marketing campaigns also benefit due to the magnitude of appeal to larger audiences.

Mass marketing also has its disadvantages. It attempts to appeal to the entire consumer population instead of focusing on a particular niche of consumers. The strength of the product and business can affect performance. The strength of the competition too has a bearing on the performance. Another factor is that

overexposure can make consumers grow tired of seeing a business's name and products everywhere.

One factor that is inevitable in mass marketing is heavy advertising costs. It is expensive to establish brands and keep them in the public eye. Often, competition is stiff. Besides, to stay ahead of the competition, high innovation and market research costs have to be incurred.

Source: <http://englishdaily626.com/comprehension.php?465>

I. Answer the following questions using complete sentences!

1. From paragraph 1, what does the product profile describe?
2. (a) From paragraph 2, what does the term mass marketing refer to?
(b) From paragraph 2, what does mass marketing ignore?
3. (a) From paragraph 3, what mass media vehicles are used in mass marketing?
(b) From paragraph 3, mention the **two** advantages of using mass media.
4. (a) From paragraph 6, what is planned obsolescence? How is it beneficial?
(b) From paragraph 7, what are the biggest advantages of Mass Marketing?
5. "Mass marketing has its disadvantages."
(a) Identify one of the disadvantages.
(b) What is this constantly increased? How?

II. Based on the passage, write a summary on the following topics :

- The necessity of mass marketing.
- The role that it plays in modern society.

UNIT – 2

Persuasive Communication

<https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fglobalgyan.in%2Fcommunicate-effectively%2F&psig=AOvVaw1beyF-i-TgX-l1HbbYeOHU&ust=1607114548721000&source=images&cd=vfe&ved=0CAIQjRxqFwoTCKj304Pasu0CFQAAAAAdAAAAABAK>

The word “persuasive” derives from the Latin word “persuas” meaning ‘convinced by reasoning’ (etymonline.com). According to Oxford English Dictionary it means, “use reasoning or argument to make someone believe or do something”.

1. LISTENING

Pre-Task:

I. Can you identify a word that is synonymous with the word “persuade”?

CLUE: C _ N _ _ N _ _

As a young entrepreneur striving to establish your firm, let us suppose you notice your employee conversing with a customer to sell a new product (i.e.) a smart watch.

II. Match the pictures with the suitable statements:

Note: Write the picture number next to the befitting statement that is provided in the grid.

C _ N _ _ N _ _	PERSUADE
Employee: Hello Sir/Madam! a. This is our new product. It has additional features like	Employee: d. Sir/ Madam, you may place your order soon as we have limited products in this

<p>a smart phone. b. This is an upgraded version. c. Most of our customers prefer this slim and sleek model.</p>	<p>model. e. Thank you Sir/ Madam. Happy Purchase!</p>
--	---

5

3

1

2

4

Persuasion is an everyday activity. It is inevitably present in all domains. It is a requirement not just in professional space but also in personal zones. There is a distinction in the act of persuading a customer to buy a product and in setting forth a business proposal to one's colleague. Apparently, it could be classified as formal persuasion and informal persuasion. When representing an idea relevant to formal presentations,

yielding to the demands of the clients/ an authority, or team meetings can be characterized as formal persuasion. Whereas, the casual interactions with professionals, discussions, sharing of ideas in e- mail, informal team meetings etc. could be identified as informal persuasion. Though there are several instances the primary factor is the way in which it can be made effective for a desired outcome in the field of advertising, business and management. It is as follows:

- i. to be attentive to the needs of the customer/ recipient
- ii. to understand their position

- iii. finally, yielding to act upon

However, to avoid rebuff it is essential to be aware of the benefits which in a client relationship or a customer service, is evident through accountability and credibility.

A word in earnest is as good as a speech

- Charles Dickens

Key Term defined:

A product launch refers to the act of launching a new product or an innovative upgrade of an existing product of a company, in the market. It need not be just products but also services. The product is displayed and its features are highlighted. It addresses the need of customers who are awaiting to buy the product. It happens to be one of the purposes of an organization or the ultimate outcome of persuasion.

Source Passage

Transcript of Steve Jobs' Speech on the Product Launch of iPhone

On January 9, 2007, Apple's CEO Steve Jobs introduced the iPhone for the first time, thereby, bringing in a remarkable change in the world of mobile devices.

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Steve_Jobs_presents_iPhone.jpg

"This is the day I've been looking forward to, for two and a half years". Once in a while, a revolutionary product comes along to change everything and Apple has been one of its kind. It has been very fortunate to work on these revolutionary products and introduce it to the world. When Macintosh was introduced in 1984 it didn't just change Apple but the entire computer industry. Similarly, the first iPod which was set in motion in 2001 revolutionized the music industry.

Well, today we are launching three revolutionary products of this class. The first one is a **widescreen iPod with touch controls**. The second is a **revolutionary mobile phone** and the third is a breakthrough **Internet communications device**. These are not three different devices. All of these are in one device, and we call it **iPhone**.

Today, Apple is going to reinvent phone. This was possible because of heeding the fact that smartphones are definitely a bit smarter, but they are actually harder to use. They are really complicated. Just for the basic operation people have a hard time figuring out how to use it. Therefore, we wanted to make a leapfrog product that is way smarter than any mobile device has ever been and super-easy to use. Now, we begin with the revolutionary user interface. It is the result of years of research and development. Of course, it's an interplay of hardware and software. We are lucky enough to initiate one more revolutionary user interface as done in the past, such as the **mouse** and the **click wheel**. Now, we are introducing **multi-touch** to the market. So, a revolutionary user

interface. We are going to build on top of it with software. Almost 30 years ago, Alan said, "People who are really serious about software should make their own hardware." This is how we feel about it.

<https://singjupost.com/steve-jobs-iphone-2007-presentation-full-transcript/?singlepage=1>

Task 1:

Answer the following questions:

1. What does CEO stand for?
2. What is exceptional about the product launched?
3. What do you know about Steve Jobs? List out the traits which you consider to be the reason for his success.
4. Does this passage sound persuasive or convincing?
5. Point out the factors that set the tone of this passage as persuasive/convincing.

Task 2:

Attempt a vocabulary enrichment task by providing 3 synonyms for each of the following words whose meaning has been given in the glossary. Examples have been given, a word each:

	Source Words	Synonyms
1.	break through	advance,
2.	remarkable	phenomenal
3.	figure out	solve
4.	fortunate	lucky
5.	heed	notice
6.	initiate	commence
7.	set in motion	launch
8.	revolutionary	progressive

Glossary:

breakthrough- an important discovery or development.

figuring out- to calculate the cost of something; to solve; to plan or think of something.

fortunate- favoured by luck.

heed- pay attention to

initiate- to begin

interplay- the way in which one has an effect on the other;

interaction

leapfrog product- an innovation of the company leading to get to a higher position or rank.

revolutionary product- product that brings in a great change affecting large numbers of people.

set in motion- to start an enterprise; to introduce a new product

user interface- refers to the means by which the user and computer system interacts

Post- Task:

Divide the class into small groups and each group should assign a role to the other.

Step 1: Ask one of the group members to play the role of a CEO. The name of this role has to be suggested by the assigning team.

Step 2: The team member assigned to role-play has to introduce a new product in the market. It can be their own imaginary product.

2. Speaking

The spoken discourse or speaking skill is given due prominence in business communication. It is the key to open the doors of international avenues in the world of commerce and management studies. In order to access this key and materialize the vision of becoming a successful entrepreneur/ business executive/ team leader/ manager, one's persuasive skills have to be honed. It is not a skill to be developed over night nor an easy job to face an unfamiliar group without prior exposure. It demands confidence and an ability to overcome fear to speak boldly and think rationally.

*"What use is a sword to a coward
Or learning to the tongue-tied?"*
-Tiruvalluvar (Kural 726)

The pre-requisites of persuasion are:

- i. maintaining a balanced emotional quotient, that is, emotional intelligence.
- ii. listening to the speaker is paramount.
- iii. ability to reason out logically
- iv. resulting in a good rapport established between the clients, customers for a better work environment.

<https://pxhere.com/en/photo/1449493>

Pre- Task:

I. Read the following instance and offer your suggestions:

In order to promote your large scale retailing you have to grab the loyal clients of niche products, sold online. Remember that the firm has carved a niche market for itself in retaining its customers.

1. What are the techniques you would adopt to succeed in this appeal to loyal customers?
2. How will you convince your new clients to action?

Glossary:

niche market -a market in which there is little or no competition for a particular type of product or service for which there is limited demand.

emotional intelligence - the ability of a person to understand, control and use their feelings and to understand the feelings of others.

factsheet - a paper or a small book giving information about a product or service.

paramount - chief in importance.

proliferate - increase or expand.

rapport - to understand each other and communicate well.

retailing - the business of selling goods to the public especially through shops/stores.

JAM – Just a Minute

This could also be called impromptu speech or an extempore. According to Oxford English Dictionary, impromptu means “without preparation or rehearsal”. In other words, it refers to speech that evolves spontaneously. It is adopted as a filtering process in interviews for jobs and for professional courses in higher education. This task aims at developing the speaking skills of the learners by providing an opportunity to prepare themselves to

unfamiliar situations such as job interviews and to gain familiarity with this challenging phase. Here are few tips to equip oneself before attempting impromptu speech which has to be in just a minute.

- Use simple and precise sentences. Let a sentence be, not more than 8-10 words.
- The speech should have an opening, middle and a conclusion.
- Overall, the impromptu should be between 100-150 words and not exceeding

this limit.

- Do not glide over words due to time constraints.

<https://www.needpix.com/photo/91784/interviewer-chat-show-host-characters-cute-job-interview-man-microphone-people>

- Try to articulate words clearly and be audible.
- Avoid using fillers while speaking
- Be spontaneous and fluent without any pause.

Certainly, your impromptu speech becomes a success when taking the above factors into consideration.

A sample draft of an impromptu has been given below, for your reference.

E- commerce:

E- commerce implies Electronic commerce. It refers to the business of buying and selling things or products online. In other words, it indicates the act of doing business online. There are four types of E- commerce business models. They are,

1. Business to Consumer- B2C
2. Business to Business- B2B
3. Consumer to Business- C2B
4. Consumer to Consumer- C2C

The most common approaches in these types of e-commerce are: direct customer service, wholesaling and drop shipping.

So, the advantages of electronic commerce could be stated as follows:

- It is collaborative, therefore, the pace in delivering products seem to be fast.

<https://pixabay.com/vectors/store-online-ecommerce-shopping-4156934/>

- It has brought the producers and consumers under one roof. Thereby, the customer services are done at ease.
- It does not have limitations in accessibility as it is user- friendly.
- The purchase could be confirmed through text messages and
- The delivery status can be easily tracked.
- Significantly, payment could be made from one's own space.

Thus, the proliferating online users have contributed towards its massive growth making it the standard way of life.

Task 1:

Perform a mock interview JAM session by choosing one of the topics listed below:

1. Win- win strategy
2. Persuasive Techniques in Marketing
3. Role of drop shipping
4. Online retailing
5. Stay Hungry. Stay Foolish- a life changing quote
6. Intricacies of a company- client relationship
7. If I were to be an Economist!
8. Role of social networking sites in product branding
9. Advocating a factsheet
10. Purpose of Emotional Intelligence

Note: It is a peer pairtask, therefore the fellow member is expected to share one's observation on their impromptu speech soon after the performance.

The outcome of this task would be:

- gaining confidence to speak in front of an audience group/public
- overcoming fear
- developing enthusiasm to perform more
- enhancing non-verbal cues
- motivating to perform well in presentations and in any form of oral testing.

Debate:

It can be defined as a structured argument. Debate is one of the types of conversation. While JAM is one- way communication, Debate involves communication between two individuals or two groups.

Task 2:

State True/ False for the following statements which differentiate a Debate from an impromptu speech (JAM):

	DEBATE	T/F	JAM	T/F
1.	It is a prepared speech		It is spontaneous	
2.	It is persuasive		It is argumentative	
3.	It is commonly used by recruiters in interviews.		It demands attention to non-verbal cues while speaking.	
4.	It has scope for critical thinking.		It promotes logical thinking.	
5.	It has time constraints.		It does not have time constraints.	

Post- Task:

Elicit your response if you were placed in this situation. You are assured of a job if you succeed in persuading your fellow interviewee to join the recruiting company for a nominal salary fixed by the concern which is not satisfactory.

Note: This task has been provided to give you a taste of reality. Similar innovative tasks have been employed by recruiters in today's job market.

3. Reading

Make it simple. Make it memorable.
Make it inviting to look at. Make it
fun to read.

- Leo Burnett

One of the important modes of communication in marketing is Advertising. Its primary aim is to persuade customers. An advertisement tends to be considered persuasive when it leads to a desired action (i.e.) by arousing the interest of the customers and inducing them to purchase the product. There are informative ads as well as persuasive ads (advertisements).

The success of an advertisement is determined by several factors.

- It has to be simple and precise as it hones memorability
- It has to grab the reader's attention
- It can be the tone, imagery, colours or symbols used in the ad
- It can be the language style and background.
- It can be the innovative way of presenting it and making it unique.

In advertising campaigns, the ubiquitous influence of a persuasive message is quite significant.

<https://www.skyramtechnologies.com/blog/facebook-plans-to-launch-ads-with-whatsapp-through-targeted-advertising/>

Pre-Task:

Step 1: Retrospect to recall the advertisement that has been a

favourite and memorable one. It can be either a television ad or an advertisement in print.

Step 2: If it is a print ad, sketch it and share it with your group members.

If it were to be a television ad, summarize the details to your group members.

Step 3: The listeners are expected to raise questions enquiring the

Glossary:

appease- to pacify

captivating- to attract and hold the interest

concise- giving information clearly and briefly

conglomerates- a corporation formed from a merger of firms

encompass- encircle; include

epitome- a perfect example

exponents- a person who holds and argues for a theory

gripping- hold firmly; hold the attention of

iconic- a famous person or an organization that people admire and see as a symbol of a particular idea or style.

infer- deduce; work out from evidence

profound- showing or requiring great insight

promulgated- make widely known

propagate- spread or transmit news

reiterate- say again or repeatedly

rhetorical- expressed so as to sound impressive; asked for effect rather than to obtain an answer

ubiquitous- found everywhere; pervasive

USP- Unique Selling Proposition, a feature of a product or service that makes it different from all others

speaker
to
articulate the
reasons
for
liking
the ad.

For example: Identify the key elements which provoked you to like the advertisement.

There are three techniques which aid in analysing the effect of an advertisement. They are advertising, rhetorical and literary techniques. Initially, it is essential to know the demographics of the target audience, and its purpose in order to promote the product. The persuasive tools are incorporated in such techniques based on the demographics of the target audience and the product. The choice of colours, imagery, background music appeals explicitly, while the emotional appeal arouses the feelings of the target group.

- Reiterating the messages through repetitive sequence.
- Use of literary devices such as end rhymes, alliteration which refers to the repetition of sounds, appeases the audience.
- A good piece of humour, shocking facts, suspense moments provokes curiosity
- Story telling or narration makes it gripping
- Further, connotation and denotation attribute meaning to the object or symbol and indicate as it is, in the ad.

For instance, when a tree is used as a symbol in the advertisement, it denotes a wood with branches and leaves and the object- tree connotes 'a united family'.

Passage

The story of an iconic old man from the largest conglomerates

This old man is an epitome encompassing a reason to smile and a season to spread happiness. This jolly man with a red suit and a white beard has had many transitions in his appearance. From a tall figure to a not-so pleasant elf form the early Santa Claus has worn Bishop's robe and even animal's skin. The cartoonist Thomas Nast drew Santa for almost 30 years, it was Nast who changed the colour of Santa's suit from tan to red. In *Harper's Weekly* which appeared in 1862, Santa had seemed to be a small elf like figure.

It was in *The Saturday Evening Post* that shopping- related ads were promulgated by *The Coca-Cola Company* initiating its Christmas advertising in the 1920s. Santa of the yester years had been sketched as stern in looks by Thomas Nast himself. Later in 1930, an ad featured the world's largest soda fountain in which a department-store Santa was distinctively attributed with a bottle of coke amongst a crowd. It was painted by an artist Fred Mizen which happened to be found in print ads during the season of Christmas in December 1930.

<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Santa-Claus>

In 1931 the Coke Company entrusted the duty of depicting a realistic and a fond version of the Santa on its advertising account executive Archie Lee. Thereafter, artist Haddon Sundblom was instructed to illustrate its "**Thirst knows no season**" advertising campaign. Eventually, Sundblom had to rely on Clement Clark Moore's poem "A Visit from St. Nicholas" (commonly called "'Twas the Night Before Christmas") published in 1822. It was Moore's poetic description that influenced Sundblom to portray a warm, cheerful and a friendly Santa Claus.

<https://jiteshpatel.co.uk/bombay-sapphire-test/>

Mere colour can speak to the soul in a thousand different ways.

- Oscar Wilde

What is a caption?

Caption may be defined as a short piece of text found below a picture in a print medium that describes the picture in a concise and captivating way. It may just denote or illustrate either the superficial or the profound meaning, if any.

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Advert_for_Pears%27 Soap Wellcome L0030380.jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Advert_for_Pears%27_Soap_Wellcome_L0030380.jpg)

Post-Task:

- I. Identify the name of the product which the caption represents.
- II. Rephrase the following captions with words that propagate it to be catchy:
 1. Go Green
Go Ford - _____
 2. Believe in the Best - _____
 3. Connecting People - _____
 4. Have a break, have a...- _____
 5. Think Different - _____
 6. Grace, space, pace - _____
 7. A Better Life, A Better World- _____

4. Writing

Writing serves to be an easy mode of persuasion. It has scope to entice the masses. The famous Greek philosopher Aristotle posits three ways to make a persuasive appeal. It is, **Ethos, pathos and logos** which implies personal credibility, empathy and logical argument. These are inter-related and correspond to the other in a sequential order. In gaining credibility the persuader ought to establish a sense of understanding others' point of view. In doing so, the one being persuaded yields to accepting the opinions or ideas of the persuader.

Finally, the pivotal role of persuasion unfolds through the logical arguments put forth by the persuader, in order to explicit the views which the recipient has to understand. This leads to reliability on being credible (i.e.) ethos, ability to understand others' point of view (i.e.) empathy, thereby, succumbing to observe the value (i.e.) logos. It is from the Greek words "dia" and "logos" meaning "through words".

<https://davidwangel.com/the-opportune-conflict/2016/12/28/the-four-types-of-conversations-debate-dialogue-discourse-and-diatribes>

Dialogue Writing:

Dialogue Writing implies two-way conversation. It is to express or convey information or exchange ideas which in fact develops relationships. Dialogue Writing exhibits the qualities, inner motives of the character and also the place of action. Dialogues when explicated in writing, could serve dual purpose. It can be filler dialogues, dialogues with a logical effect or without a logical impact.

Dialogues evoke a feel of reality when it gains proximity to the characters and adheres to the main theme. It can be persuasive when it has an element of surprise, an emotional appeal or an awaited moment.

Pre-Task:

Attempt dialogue writing between a manufacturer and a customer where the latter provides customer feedback. Use the hints provided below to develop a

Glossary:

adhere- support a cause or belief

adversity- hardship

argumentative- discussion involving disagreement; a reason put forward

attribute- characteristic quality

authenticate- prove the authenticity which is known to be true

credibility- believable; convincing

empathy- the ability to share and understand other's feelings

fend- support yourself

frenzy- a state of excitement or agitation

procrastinator- a person who postpones action

proximity- nearness

recipient- a person who receives something

seize- take hold of forcibly or suddenly

sensational- causing great public interest

suburbs- residential area outside the central part of a town

succumb- give way to pressure or temptation

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Pre-Task:

Manufacturer (M) : Dear Customer, hope you are satisfied with our product! Please rate the quality of our product between star rating 1 and 5.

Customer (C) : Yes, I like the product so much and I wish to give _____

M:

C:
M:
C:
M:

Task 1:

Initiate a Dialogue between two colleagues about their team event. Use these words to frame a convincing conversation between the two.

C1:	advance, affordable, amazing, attractive, challenging, demand, development, easy to access, hurry, introducing, remarkable, revolutionary, sensational, stunning look, miracle, magic, offer, quick, limited, curious, effective, brand quality, establish, reasonable, consider, promoting, striving, productive, attributes, worthy, value, huge success	Hope you feel good about
-----	--	--------------------------

the upcoming event.

C2: Yes, we have been waiting for this D- day.

C1: I am looking forward to _____

C2: It is certainly going to be_____

C1: What makes you feel so certain about it?

C2: _____

C1: _____

C2: _____

Passage

Bend to Mend

I have to accentuate the fact that I had finally attained my dream job. I have been hired as a budget analyst at my favourite magazine. The nature of my job demands working for the business manager. Also, to be a liaison between the finance and marketing departments, to develop sales and the workplace environment. At present, as I stand in this bakery which indeed is memorable. It was in this place I had celebrated my new job with my senior

editors, both finance and marketing team three months ago. Unfortunately, it was a shocking moment as our publication manager explained the status of our publishing house which had to be shut down as it was in dearth of business.

As we were trying to pack our things at the office, I could notice people walking around desperately and in a frenzy way. There were 17 other employees like me, with the same plight. Subsequently, I had to leave my apartment and move into the suburbs which was quite economic. It took almost 6 months to seize my new dream. It was from these times of adversity that I gained the ability to embrace my situation and learnt the importance of adaptability. If there prevails a similar storm in future, I know how to bend, to mend and to fend myself.

Task 2:

1. Identify the persuasive words in this passage.
2. State the overall tone of the passage.
3. What are the qualities that contributed towards the restoring process?
4. What will be your approach if you were to be in the narrator's position?

Post- Task:

Draft an argumentative essay on any one of the topics:

1. A proactive leader can never be a procrastinator.
2. Digital India- a sign of progress.
3. Persuasion is a tactic or a tool to appeal.
4. Advertisements determine the success of a product.
5. HRs are the central collaborators within a work place.

Note: The following list of argumentative words may be employed in the essay.

compare, commence, contrast, decide, infer, in my opinion, agree/ disagree, assume, factual, oppose, approve, authenticate, disprove, deny, refuse, withdraw, insist, expect, disappoint, strategic, rapport, misunderstand, disproportionate, consistent

You Tube Resources:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t4S6cHZD3x4>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iAkUT2LcMSY>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6HTj-Wlft9I>

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Unit - 3

PROFESSIONAL ENGLISH FOR COMMERCE AND MANAGEMENT UNIT III – DIGITAL COMPETENCE

LISTENING

Session 1:

ACTIVE LISTENING: Active listening is when we can listen, repeat, paraphrase and reflect on what we listen to. Active listening also involves watching the speaker's body language. In videos, it is also important to notice what is written on the screen.

Active listening involves the following steps:

Repeating

- Repeating words/phrases exactly as used by the speaker.

Paraphrasing

- Using similar words/ideas to summarise what the speaker stated.

Reflecting

- Reflecting on what the speaker said to suit your context/needs

Pre-Task (Vocabulary):

Recipe	brand ambassador	turban	demise
metropolitan cities	trending	concept	basmati rice
seeraga samba rice	imported		

Match the words in the box with the images given below and write their meaning:

Activity:

Watch the following video where NagasamyDhanabalan speaks to YourStory.com founder, Shradha Sharma about DindigulThalappakatti and its origins. While listening to the video, write down key words or ideas that you think are important.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4yvB0_z8Ydc

I. Repeat: Can you recollect some of the dates, names and places that NagasamyDhanabalan mentioned in his talk?

These questions might help you repeat the facts:

1. Who started Thalappakatti Biryani and when?
2. What was Thalappakatti first called?
3. When did NagasamyDhanabalan's grandfather pass away?
4. When did he first come to Chennai?
5. From 2009 till 2017 (when the interview was taken), how many branches of Thalappakatti Biryani were there?

II. Paraphrase: List at least 4-5 key points about the origins of Thalappakatti Biryani.

1. What inspired NagasamyDhanabalan's grandfather to start a restaurant?
2. What inspired NagasamyDhanabalan to bring Thalappakatti to Chennai?
3. According to the speaker, what were the unique contributions of Thalappakatti to the Chennai food scene?
4. How did Thalappakatti change the way biriyani was consumed?

5. What was the traditional manner of cooking biriyani and how did Thalappakatti have to change their method?

III. Reflect:

1. According to you, has Thalappakatti made a difference in Chennai? If so, how?
2. Do you think, as Mr. Dhanabalan does, that Thalappakatti is a unique restaurant? Can you think of other competitors who make equally good or better Biriyani?
3. Is this video, according to you, a promotional video? If so, why?

Session 2:

INTERVIEWS:An interview consists of an interviewer (who asks the questions) and an interviewee (who responds). Interviews are often conducted to hire employees for jobs. They are also conducted by journalists or other interested business people to find out more about the achievements of their peers. Though an interview is usually formal and focuses on the work that one has achieved, it can involve some questions regarding the interviewee’s backstory and personal life.

Pre-Task (Vocabulary):

Match the following words or phrases with their meaning:

1. Despite	i. electronic payments that are processed within seconds and credited from one bank to another without any intermediary
2. hassles	ii. A model of an actual or proposed machine that can do on a small-scale, the work that the actual machine is supposed to do.
3. unorganized agriculture supply chain	iii. Changes to existing processes between the production of a product and its final consumption with a claim to make it environmentally and financially sustainable. This involves product design, material selection, manufacturing,

		packaging, transport, distribution and consumption etc.
4. sustainable supply chain	iv.	To know something thoroughly or completely
5. instant payments	v.	Obstacles or challenges
6. Logistics	vi.	Influenced or inspired
7. Implement	vii.	The quality or ability to be able to do something
8. prototype	viii.	The value of shares issued by a company
9. working models	ix.	The determination to do something
10. Operate	x.	To begin from a point where nothing has been done before
11. Dilute	xi.	The progress of a start-up company and the momentum it gains as the business grows
12. seed funding	xii.	In spite of/ regardless of
13. Traction	xiii.	the commercial activity of transporting goods to customers
14. "in and out"	xiv.	To put a plan into action
15. Acuity	xv.	Function
16. Resolve	xvi.	To weaken the strength or quality of something
17. Capability/capacity	xvii.	The capital that an investor invests in a start-up company
18. "start from scratch"	xviii.	The first model/design from which other forms will be developed
19. Hurdles	xix.	The various jobs between the harvesting of a crop to the final sale to the consumers undertaken by daily wage workers or various farmers.
20. Motivated	xx.	A complicated and inconvenient situation

Activity:

Watch the following interview of Agrowave CEO Anu Meena. The interview is conducted by Kalyan from *The Business Monk*.

While listening to the interview, notice the following:

- a. The interviewer introduces the interviewee.
- b. The conversation is focused on the interviewee's job, inspiration and success.
- c. The conversation is specific to Agrowave, but also gives general tips on start-up companies and what start-up entrepreneurs should look out for.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4IQUz4Q1n-o>

I. Answer the following:

1. What is the role of Agrowave?
2. What were some of the struggles Anu Meena faced before starting her company?
3. Why did Anu Meena start Agrowave?
4. According to Anu Meena, what does it take to transform an idea into a working prototype model?
5. What does she say about team work and building a team?
6. How did Anu Meena manage to raise funds? Was it the common thing to do?
7. Would you consider Agrowave a successful start-up?
8. According to you, what is the most important take away from the interview?

Note:

Interviews can also be screened without the interviewer.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2TzhISiXtno>(Video optional)

Or they can be held in the form of a panel:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E77dWCsOrr8>(Video optional)

SPEAKING

Session 1:

CONDUCTING AND PARTICIPATING IN AN ONLINE

INTERVIEW: Nowadays, many interviews of entrepreneurs are conducted online, using platforms such as Zoom or Google Meet. It is, therefore, important to know some of the features of these video conferencing sites and how they can be used while conducting/participating in an interview. The person who starts the Zoom or Google Meet session is the host, and the others are participants.

Pre-Task(Exploring video conferencing sites):

Features explored: Record, background, share screen, audio (on/off), participant list, using the chat box

Write the function of each of the features (When and why are the following features used?):

I. Zoom:

A.

1. Audio: _____

2. Video: _____

3. Security: _____

4. Participants: _____

5. Chat: _____

6. Share screen: _____

7. Record: _____

8. Reactions: _____

9. End call: _____

B:

II. Google Meet:

A:

1. Security: _____

2. Audio: _____

3. Video: _____

4. Raise Hand: _____

5. Turn on Captions: _____

6. Present Now: _____

7. Options: _____

8. Participants: _____

9. Chat Box: _____

B:

1. Record: _____

2. Layout: _____

3. Full Screen: _____

4. Background: _____

5. Participants: _____

6. Messages: _____

7. Chat Box: _____

Activity:
Work in groups to form an interview panel. The interviewer will conduct

Points to remember

- The interviewer should prepare questions beforehand.
- The interviewee should anticipate possible questions, and prepare themselves to face these questions. Answer with honesty and accuracy.
- As the interview will be conducted online, both the interviewee and interviewer can create PPTs, or use photos or videos to enhance their presentation/conversation.
- Language used by the interviewer: reporting (give some information about your panellists before you begin) and requesting (ask the panellists to talk about themselves; guide the flow of the conversation)
- Language used by the interviewee: Give explanations and lot of examples; make your response formal; use business terminology to explain the way your start-up functions

Ensure that your body language is professional.

an interview of young start-ups in the small-scale enterprises sector. The other panellists will pitch their ideas, and the possible challenges they might face while creating their start-up business.

INTERVIEWER	INTERVIEWEE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction ▪ Mr./Ms. _____ works as a... ▪ S(he) began her/his journey as... ▪ Questions ▪ Could you talk about...? ▪ Can you tell us your experience when...? ▪ What did you feel when...? ▪ What inspired you to...? ▪ When did you decide to...? ▪ Can you describe your typical day? ▪ What were the challenges...? ▪ How did you overcome...? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ I'm excited by the business opportunities... ▪ I really enjoy... ▪ We contribute/The company contributes to... ▪ We need to keep an eye on/watch out for... ▪ I was always inspired by... ▪ My (parent/friend/sibling) motivated me to... ▪ My (parent/friend/sibling) stood by me when... <p style="margin-top: 10px;">Some business terminology that</p>

<p>You can find more questions on https://www.livecareer.com/resources/interviews/questions/entrepreneurial-informational-interviewing</p> <p>https://billionsuccess.com/how-to-interview-entrepreneurs/</p>	<p>can be used can be viewed here:</p> <p>https://abdoriani.com/91-startup-terms-every-entrepreneur-should-know/</p>
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Present your interview panel in front of the class.

Session 2:

CREATING A VLOG: Vlogging or Video Blogging is a means of using video streaming channels such as YouTube in order to share information. Vlogging can be used to talk about your product or your company.

Pre-Task:

Watch the following vlog: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O0-Ofd_9egE. This video is a good example of a professional vlogger (C4ETech), who reviews technical gadgets. Based on the video, work in groups and discuss the various aspects of creating a vlog and what (according to you) makes a successful vlog.

Activity:

In the same groups, work together to create a vlog.

Steps involved in creating a Vlog:

- **Pick your content-** what is your start-up about? What are the various aspects of your company that you can talk about? Write down a list. You need a core idea that runs throughout your Vlog. Do you want to write about clothes, technology, industries, industrial processes, marketing processes? The field is vast. So be sure to choose wisely.
- **Do some research-** who are the others who are talking about similar products/companies online? Watch some successful vloggers.

Try not to imitate them completely. Also browse YouTube for what works, and what doesn't.

- **Equipment-** make sure that the camera, lighting and audio suit the needs of your vlog. You can either film your vlog from a desk, or while travelling, for which purpose a simple camera is enough. Make sure your background stands out and attracts the audience. Focus the light on you- you are the star of your vlog. Reduce external sounds, and ensure that the mic is placed close to you.
- **Create an official channel on YouTube-**
 - Sign in to YouTube with an official Google account.
 - Click on the Profile icon.
 - Select "Create a Channel".
 - Fill out the details to name your new channel and verify your account.
 - Click Done.
- **Build your brand-** Upload a professional photo (make sure it relates to your company/product). Confidently talk to the camera. If you are talking about a specific place or event, show images to support your content. Explore editing software to help you with your vlog.
- **Keep your videos short.**

Links to help you:

<https://support.google.com/youtube/answer/1646861?hl=en-GB>

<https://newbluefx.com/blog/create-vlogs-9-easy-steps/>

<https://makeawebsitehub.com/how-to-start-a-vlog/>

You can take ideas from the following list:

- ✓ Any technical gadget
- ✓ Clothes/ make-up/ accessories
- ✓ Your own start-up idea
- ✓ Tips on using home appliances
- ✓ A cooking video
- ✓ A review of a company or entrepreneur

who inspires you

- ✓ Some of your creative work- art/music

(Remember to keep it professional!)

READING

Session 1:

DIGITAL COMPETENCE: Digital competence is the ability to use ICT with ease—this includes technical skills as well as social and emotional skills in using digital platforms/technologies.

Pre-Task (Vocabulary):

1. Inescapable	i. Shortened form of a word/phrase
2. Digital divide	ii. Protocol/manners
3. Digital literacy	iii. Someone/something providing a lot of information
4. Digital competence	iv. The gap between those who have access to computers/internet and those who don't
5. "Yawning gap"	v. Unable to avoid
6. Etiquette	vi. Knowledgeable
7. Abbreviations	vii. An all-inclusive wide understanding of ICT which includes technical skills as well as social and emotional skills required to ethically and safely use digital

	platforms
8. "made it big"	viii. A very wide gap that is extremely difficult to reduce
9. "Mine of information"	ix. One's ability to find and use information using various digital platforms (technical skills)
10. savvy	x. Have become very successful/popular

Activity:

Read the article on "Digital Competence for Academic and Professional Excellence" given below and answer the questions that follow:

Digital Competence for Academic and Professional Excellence

It is an inescapable fact that in this globalized world, the internet, wireless networks, cell phones, laptops, tabs, and social networking has come to stay. In such an increasingly digital era, knowledge and competence of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) is extremely important. Digital competence, therefore, involves the knowledge and skills required to use ICT with ease and comfort. This implies that individuals do not only require technical skills, but also social and emotional skills to handle digital platforms. For instance, it is no longer enough to know how to use WhatsApp, but also to understand the spread of fake news, or the nuances of User Rights when it comes to communicating via the platform. Another example is regarding the content a user uploads on their social media platforms—often, without realizing the implication, users upload personal content which is could be viewed by their professional circles.

Simultaneously, we should be aware that, as the India CSR Network notes, of the 4.5 billion people across the globe who are still not connected to the internet, more than 4 billion belong to developing nations. In countries such

as India, there is a huge digital divide, despite which individuals are expected to gain digital competence for academic and professional success. According to an article published in *The Hindu*, only 20% of Indians above the age of 5 years have basic digital literacy.

On one hand, this yawning digital divide creates a huge challenge for those who do not have access to digital technologies. On the other, businesses have an increased demand for individuals who are digitally competent. According to www.digitalskillsglobal.com, some of the digital skills that businesses seek in their employees include: programming, web and app development; digital business analysis; digital design; digital project and product management; digital marketing; effective social media use; and data science and analytics. In order to reach such a level, individuals should also have an advanced competency and maturity in using basic devices or programmes such as the mobile phone, emails, social media platforms etc. For instance, an interesting brand called Casper Sleep Channel, uses the various platforms of Facebook, Instagram, Twitter as well as YouTube, Spotify and IGTV to promote their channel, managing to create unique ways to stand out amongst its competition.

Some of the basic digital tools that beginners need to know about include:

1. Mobile phones: Nowadays companies use WhatsApp for business communication, and knowledge of the App is necessary. Simultaneously, users should understand business etiquette when it comes to mobile phone interactions. For instance, calls can only be made during working hours. Similarly, abbreviations should not be used in official messages. With the increasing number of Smart Phones, users should also be capable of using multiple Apps in their device with fluency and speed.
2. Computers: Computers require a slightly different skill set. Users ought to know the importance of MS Word, PowerPoint, Excel etc. The use of e-mails in a professional capacity is also significant.
3. Social Media: Social media platforms play a very important role in business strategies and these platforms need to be used innovatively in

order to boost sales and promotion. Many artists have made it big in the field just through their YouTube channels or Instagram pages.

4. The Internet: This vast mine of information and data has to be used wisely in order to support businesses.

In the field of academia, too, such digital knowledge will only aid students in learning more in lesser time. The internet, is a source of great information—but the trick is to know where to search, and how to verify your content.

While these digital tools are important, the landscape of both technology as well as business needs to be kept in mind. Technology can be a boon for many enterprises, but the increased cost of certain technological gadgets, or the amount of time and money spent on tech-based marketing can be a drain, especially on small-scale businesses. Since consumers are often swamped with data via online platforms, it becomes difficult for small-scale enterprises to reach the level of digital advancement maintained by larger, multinational organisations. www.smallbusiness.chron.com notes some of the major obstacles faced by small businesses in this vast field. It is because of the competitive nature of the digital space that being digitally savvy will work towards the advantage of both students as well as employees.

Sources:

https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/Building_Digital_Competencies_to_Benefit/GwiwDWA_AQBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=digital+competence&pg=PA3&printsec=frontcover

<https://indiacr.in/weaving-digital-competence-into-our-educational-curriculum/>

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<https://digitalskillsglobal.com/blog/the-top-10-digital-skills-tech-companies-are-looking-for-today>

<https://sproutsocial.com/insights/social-media-marketing-examples/>

<https://smallbusiness.chron.com/technologys-negative-impact-business-19118.html>

Answer the following:

1. What is digital competence?
2. What are some of the problems faced by countries such as India with regard to the digital competence of its population?

4. Responsive Design	Respo	d. Language of the text (provides the structure of the page)
5. RSS	Favico	e. RSS is a type of web feed which gives users the ability to get immediate updates from websites in a standardized, computer-readable format
6. Favicon	Domai	f. Small text files containing basic information about the pages you visit.
7. User Experience Design	UX	g. The file address of a resource on the Internet, including a web page, an image, a video, a style sheet etc.
8. Accessibility	Cache	h. The ability of a website to be used by people with disabilities
9. Mobile Design	Cookie	i. A layout designed to suit various devices (e.g. phone, laptop, tab etc.)
10. CSS	Databa	j. Style sheet language (language of the page design/layout)
11. URL (Uniform Resource Locator)	URL	k. A unique name that identifies a

		website
12. er	Brows	l. Manage the creation and modification of digital content (E.g. WordPress)
13. (Content Management Systems)	CMS	m. The record maintained by your browser of the pages you visit- a device's temporary storage space
14. Feed (Really Simple Syndication)	RSS	n. Icon that appears next to your domain name in the browser address bar

Activity: Read the "Overview" of the Kerala State Poverty Eradication Mission, "Kudumbashree" and answer the questions that follow:

<https://kudumbashree.org/pages/7>

Kudumbashree, the Kerala State Poverty Eradication Mission was launched on 17th May 1998 inaugurated by the Prime Minister, Shri Atal Bihari Vajpayee. The Mission aims to eradicate absolute poverty within a definite time frame of 10 years under the leadership of Local Self Governments formed and empowered by the 73rd and 74th Amendments of the Constitution of India. The Mission launched by the State Government with the active support of Government of India and NABARD has adopted a different methodology in addressing poverty by organizing the poor in to community-based organizations. The Mission follows a process approach rather than a project approach.

Kudumbashree, a community organization of Neighborhood Groups (NHGs) of women in Kerala, has been recognized as an effective strategy for the empowerment of women in rural as well as urban areas: bringing women together from all spheres of life to fight for their rights or for empowerment.

The overall empowerment of women is closely linked to economic empowerment. Women through these NHGs work on a range of issues such as health, nutrition, agriculture, etc. besides income generation activities and seeking micro credit.

Kudumbashree differs from conventional programmes in that it perceives poverty not just as the deprivation of money, but also as the deprivation of basic rights. The poor need to find a collective voice to help claim these rights.

Kudumbashree was conceived as a joint programme of the Government of Kerala and Nabard implemented through Community Development Societies (CDSs) of Poor Women, serving as the community wing of Local Governments. Kudumbashree is formally registered as the "State Poverty Eradication Mission" (SPEM), a society registered under the Travancore Kochi Literary, Scientific and Charitable Societies Act 1955. It has a governing body chaired by the State Minister of LSG. There is a state mission with a field officer in each district. This official structure supports and facilitates the activities of the community network across the state. Kudumbashree differs from conventional programmes in that it perceives poverty not just as the deprivation of money, but also as the deprivation of basic rights. The poor need to find a collective voice to help claim these rights.

The grassroots of Kudumbashree are Neighbourhood Groups (NHG in short) that send representatives to the ward level Area Development Societies (ADS). The ADS sends its representatives to the Community Development Society (CDS), which completes the unique three-tier structure of Kudumbashree. Today, there are 2.77 lakhs NHGs, over 19,854 ADSs and 1073 CDSs in Kudumbashree.

It is this network that brings women to the Grama Sabhas and helps them bring the needs of the poor to the attention of the local governments. The Community Development Societies are also very active in Government programmes and play significant roles in development activities ranging from socio-economic surveys and enterprise development to community management and social audit.

Though its efforts to engage women in civil society in development issues and opportunities, Kudumbashree in association with the local self government of Kerala is charting out new meaning and possibilities for local economic development and citizen centric governance.

MISSION

There are two distinguishing characteristics to Kudumbashree which set it apart from the usual SHG model of empowerment. These are,

1.The universality of reach – from its very inception Kudumbashree has attempted to bring every poor woman in the state within its fold, as a consequence of which today Kudumbashree is present in every village panchayat and municipality, and in nearly every ward, colony and hamlet. The sheer spread is mind boggling, and it is only because the local community of women drive the system that it has managed to persevere.

2.The scope of community interface in local governance – the functioning of Kudumbashree is tied up to the development initiatives of the local government be it for social infrastructure, welfare or right based interventions or for employment generation. From food security to health insurance, from housing to enterprise development, from the national wage employment programme to the jagratha samiti, every development experience depends on Kudumbashree to provide the community interface.

It is using these opportunities that Kudumbashree strives to convert a microfinance led financial security model into a more comprehensive model of local economic development.

THE MISSION STATEMENT

To eradicate absolute poverty in ten years through concerted community action under the leadership of local governments, by facilitating organization of the poor for combining self-help with demand-led convergence of available services and resources to tackle the multiple dimensions and manifestations of poverty, holistically.

VISION

Kudumbashree strives to develop the model of a micro finance led financial security process into a more comprehensive model of local economic development under the aegis of local governments. This would hopefully sustain the transformation of the local governance agenda from welfare to entitlement. Such a transformation does not come about easily and requires rewriting established administrative and development practices

It requires the community acquiring voice and being heard. It requires institutionalizing processes that allow for participation and meaningful contribution. And when we speak of community we speak of the people for whom government is a palpable entity influencing the quality of their lives, as well as of the people on the periphery, both social and physical, for whom manifold deprivations have snuffed out hope of change.

We speak of the women who are finding, through collective endeavours, the stepping stones leading from participation to citizenship in its truest sense. It is through the realization of citizenship that Kudumbashree would be able to significantly address issues of equity and justice.

Answer the following:

1. When was the Kerala State Poverty Eradication Mission established?
2. Whose help did the Kerala State Government seek to launch Kudumbashree?
3. What is the "different methodology" used by the Kerala State Government in addressing poverty?
4. What do the following abbreviations stand for?-
NHG
CDS
SPEM
ADS
5. What are the various issues that women work on?
6. According to the website, how many NHGs, CDSs and ADSs are now a part of Kudumbashree?
7. What is the significance of the three-tier approach of Kudumbashree?
8. What are the two distinguishing characteristics of Kudumbashree's mission?

9. How is the spread of Kudumbashree's branches unique?
10. How does the programme attempt to alter the microfinance led financial security model?
11. What is Kudumbashree's Mission Statement?

WRITING

Session 1:

CREATING A WEBSITE: A website helps you to promote your company. It is important to tell viewers a little bit about the company, the team, who began the company (the founder or CEO), the vision and mission of the company, as well as some of the company's achievements. This helps gain the trust of viewers.

Pre-Task:

Create a mind-map of everything that you think is necessary to include in your webpage. A mind-map is a visual organisation of your thoughts. It looks somewhat like this:

This is not exhaustive, and you can add to this mind-map, or create your own.

Activity:

Using the mind-map you have drawn, create the content for a webpage for either a company or product that you would like to promote.

How to Create a Webpage

- **Content:** Make sure you know what your website is about.
- **Choose a website builder:** Some options can be viewed at <https://www.websitetooltester.com/en/blog/best-free-website-builders/>
- **Write an "About Us" page:** Describe the Vision and Mission of your company.
- **Write about your team:** the founder and other members

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TY PROFESSIONAL ENGLISH FOR COMMERCE & MANAGEMENT - II

Unit – 4

Creativity and Imagination

Creativity

Creativity is the process of translating thoughts into truth, fresh and creative. The capacity to look the universe in various directions, locate secret trends, connect otherwise unrelated phenomena and develop ideas. Creativity requires two processes i.e., perception, and development.

Imagination

Imagination is the capacity to develop and construct in the mind, without any instant senses, new topics, sensations, and concepts. It is also defined as the development of experiences in one's mind that can re-create past experiences such as vibrant memories with likely modifications, or can be invented entirely and potentially spectacular scenes. Imagination helps render knowledge suitable to solve challenges and is important to incorporate learning experiences

Enhancing Creativity

The testing and manipulation of innovative domain specific interventions that helps people to develop their imaginative thought and explore the effects of innovation in order to accomplish their objectives and well-being.(i.e., cognitive abilities, divergent thinking skills, investigating the efficacy of motivational strategies, among other tools).

Creative Thinking in Communication

Any worker in the world is well informed that innovative thought is integrated into conversation. Adequate innovation, such as creativity in decision-making, creativity in proposals, creativity in presenting ideas before others and much more resolve much of their targets. Creative thinking in communication to the logical growth of an individual and to the advantage of creative thinking in the workplace involves a variety of practice.

Problem solving Methods for Creative thinking in Communication

Creative thinking embodies behavioural subsets including interest, cognizance and responsive means to cultivate fresh concepts and problem solving approaches. The role of creative thinking required at different levels of workplace that places on the basis of communication. The segment usually studies the importance of creative thinking in making judgment, solving challenges, creating creativity, overcoming disputes and in improving leadership skills at workplaces.

Creative Thinking in Decision Making

The following suggestions can help in your Creativity thinking in decision-making process:

Recognize decisions. Decisions are more than wishes or desires. There’s a world of difference between “I wish I could be a better student” and “I will take more powerful notes, read with greater retention, and review my class notes daily.” Deciding to eat fruit for dessert instead of ice cream rules out the next trip to the ice cream store.

Establish priorities. Some decisions are trivial. No matter what the outcome, your life is not affected much. Other decisions can shape your circumstances for years. Devote more time and energy to the decisions with big outcomes.

Base decisions on a life plan. The benefit of having long-term goals for our lives is that they provide a basis for many of our daily decisions. Being certain about what we want to accomplish this year and this month makes today’s choices more clear.

Balance learning styles in decision making. To make decisions more effectively, use all four modes of learning explained in a previous lesson. The key is to balance reflection with action, and thinking with experience. First, take the time to think creatively, and generate many options. Then think critically about the possible consequences of each option before choosing one. Remember, however, that thinking is no substitute for experience. Act on your chosen option, and notice what happens. If you’re not getting the results you want, then quickly return to

(Reference1:[https://socialsci.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Counseling_and_Guidance/Book%3A_OpenNow_College_Success_\(Cengage\)/05%3A_Developing_Critical_Thinking_Skills/5.03%3A_Using_Critical_Thinking_Skills-_Decision_Making_and_Problem_Solving](https://socialsci.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Counseling_and_Guidance/Book%3A_OpenNow_College_Success_(Cengage)/05%3A_Developing_Critical_Thinking_Skills/5.03%3A_Using_Critical_Thinking_Skills-_Decision_Making_and_Problem_Solving))

(Reference2:<https://edu.gcfglobal.org/en/problem-solving-and-decision-making/what-is-critical-thinking/1/>)

Why it’s so,

Critical thinking and problem solving skills are imperative for making smatter, profitable and winning decisions or recommendations. This needs

- examining and improving your thought processes
- ask yourself some factual questions
- list out the available challenge assumptions
- consider varying view points

Source
Identified
Stage One: Identifying the Problem

Establish criteria before the options are apparent
What I need to achieve - outcome
Decision criteria – measure options against the criteria
Give weights to the options

Before being able to confront a problem its existence needs to be identified. This might seem an obvious statement but, quite often, problems will have an impact for some time before they are recognized or brought to the attention of someone who can do anything about them.

In many organizations it is possible to set up formal systems of communication so that problems are reported early on, but inevitably these systems do not always work. Once a problem has been identified, its exact nature needs to be determined: what are the goal and barrier components of the problem? Some of the main elements of the problem can be outlined, and a first attempt at defining the problem should be made. This definition should be clear enough for you to be able to easily explain the nature of the problem to others.

GOAL (I want to...)	BARRIER (but...)
Tell a friend that we find something they do irritating.	I don't want to hurt their feelings.
Buy a new computer.	I'm not sure which model to get or how much money is reasonable to spend.
Set up a new business.	I don't know where to start.

Looking at the problem in terms of goals and barriers can offer an effective way of defining many problems and splitting bigger problems into more manageable sub-problems.

Sometimes it will become apparent that what seems to be a single problem, is more accurately a series of problems. For example, in the problem: "I have been offered a job that I want, but I don't have the transport to get there and I don't have enough money to buy a car."

Problem	Working Definition
"I want to take a job, but I don't have the transport to get there and I don't have enough money to buy a car."	"I want to take this job."

- "I want to take a job" (main problem)
- "But I don't have transport to get there" (sub-problem 1)
- "And I don't have enough money to buy a car" (sub-problem 2)

During this first stage of problem solving, it is important to get an initial working definition of the problem. Although it may need to be adapted at a later stage, a good working definition makes it possible to describe the problem to others who may become involved in the problem solving process. For example:

Stage Two: Structuring the Problem

The second stage of the problem solving process involves gaining a deeper understanding of the problem. Firstly, facts need to be checked.

Problem	Checking Facts
"I want to take a job, but I don't have the transport to get there and I don't have enough money to buy a car."	"Do I really want a job?" "Do I really have no access to transport?" "Can I really not afford to buy a car?"

The questions have to be asked, is the stated goal the real goal? Are the barriers actual barriers and what other barriers are there? In this example, the problem at first seems to be:

Goal	Barrier 1	Barrier 2
Take the job	No transport	No money

This is also a good opportunity to look at the **relationships between the key elements of the problem**. For example, in the 'Job-Transport-Money' problem, there are strong connections between all the elements.

By looking at all the relationships between the key elements, it appears that the problem is more about how to achieve any one of three things, i.e. job, transport or money, because solving one of these sub-problems will, in turn, solve the others.

Creative Thinking in Solving Problems

(Example: Solving Complex Business Problems)

From planning last-minute meetings, to addressing unexpected customer queries, there is no end to the problem solving you do day in, day out. And you want to be confident in the decisions you make. To help you get started, why not take our interactive quiz and find out how good your problem-solving skills are. Then dive into the different approaches to problem solving; which ones do you use already, and which ones could be helpful in the future?

Finally, we can help you identify the causes of problems, and use problem-solving techniques to improve business processes.)

(Reference: https://www.mindtools.com/pages/main/newMN_TMC.htm)

Creative Thinking in Developing Leadership Skills

Pre-task

Mention the names of a few world Business Leaders with Strong Leadership Skills

10 Inspiring Business Leaders with Strong Leadership Skills

IndraNooyi, Former Chairman and CEO of PepsiCo -**Mirror Review Quotes**

"As a leader, I am tough on myself and I raise the standard for everybody; however, I am very caring because I want people to excel at what they are doing so that they can aspire to be me in the future".

Bill Gates, Co-Founder of Microsoft -**Pondot**

“The leader needs to create an environment in which people can analyze the situation and develop a good response”. “Great organizations demand a high level of commitment by the people involved”.

Mary Barra, Chairman and CEO of General Motors -Stanford Business

“If we win the hearts and minds of employees, we're going to have better business success”.

“It’s important to surround yourself with people who will challenge you and tell you when and why you are wrong”.

Richard Branson, Founder of Virgin Group -Virgin

“People are fundamental in driving the success of a business. If you treat your staff like the smart and capable adults they are — and give them choice to make informed decisions — you will cultivate an environment in which everyone can flourish”.

Herb Kelleher, Co-Founder of Southwest Airlines -Employers Resource

“Your employees come first. And if you treat your employees right, guess what? Your customers come back, and that makes your shareholders happy. Start with employees and the rest follows from that”.

Tim Cook, CEO of Apple - Fast Company)

“The most important thing is, do you have the courage to admit that you're wrong? And do you change? The most important thing to me as a CEO is that we keep the courage”.

SundarPichai, CEO of Google, Alphabet –Thinking Marketing

“As a leader, a lot of your job is to make those people successful. It’s less about trying to be successful (yourself), and more about making sure you have good people and your work is to remove that barrier, remove roadblocks for them so that they can be successful in what they do. So that’s how I’ve always thought about it.”

Tony Hsieh, CEO of Zappos–InnovationManagement

“I view my role more as trying to set up an environment where personalities, creativity, and individuality of all the different employees come our and can shine.”

Howard Schultz, Former Chairman and CEO of Starbucks (BusinessInsider)

“You can’t expect your employees to exceed the expectations of your customers if you don’t exceed the employees’ expectations of management.

Mark Zuckerberg, Co-Founder, Chairman and CEO of Facebook - Inc

“We look for people who are passionate about something. In a way, it almost doesn't matter what you're passionate about”.

(Reference:<https://blog.smarp.com/what-are-the-top-leadership-skills-that-make-a-great-leader>)

Embracing Creativity in Business Communication

(Reference: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h1fCJM1LMaY>)

A. Listen to the Video, audio and answer the questions given below:

1. What is a Business Communication?)
2. What do you understand by ‘effective communication’ and ‘Communication plan’ of Business?
3. What causes unpredictability in the situation on work place?
4. Briefly explain your understanding best communication in business.
5. What is the most important aspect of the business communication?

B. Listen and give specific information on the termsgiven:

1. Influential
2. Reward power

3. Filters
4. Communication Channels
5. Message Receiver, sender
6. Feedback
7. Context
8. Overarching
9. Strategic ambiguity
10. Crisis

Creative approach for communication in Business

- The solution is to try it out: Sensory pictures are a decent starting point, even though you don't feel especially imaginative, you do have to take a couple extra minutes before you click submit' your message to pepper in those excellent visuals that lit the brain rather than ordinary words.
- Boost your company communications' imagination by partnering Individual contact cooperation, you can unlock unique concepts or phrases that can render your message very different. New modes can also improve ingenious positives.

Resource :<https://youtu.be/QGeHS4jOOX0>

Listen to the above video and answer the following questions.

1. What is important according to you? - What to communicate / How to communicate?
2. What is strategic communication?
3. What are the mutual beneficial situations?
4. What are the four important steps for successful communication?
5. What is meant by communicating the value? Why is it important?

Some the real-life examples of 'creative challenges' from hatrabbits.com is given here for our discussion

- How can we double our quarterly turnover?
 - How can we get 50 new clients in market X?
 - How can we sell our expertise in different market segments?
 - How can we do our work more efficiently?
 - How can we lower the costs of process X?
 - How can we reduce the workload of our department?
 - How can we raise the team spirit in our department?
 - How can we increase the satisfaction of our employees?
 - How can we provide our customers with useful insights by using 'big data'?
- (Source: <https://hatrabbits.com/en/topics-for-creative-thinking/>)**

Read the passage carefully and make notes from it, keeping in mind the Main ideas and the subordinate points. Creativity on Co-workers in Business Communication on Management. The first one is discuss out for you side.

When it comes to communicating information to employees, video is a great tool. Something we're in the habit of at Screen Cloud is ensuring that if we can make a video or screen-recording to share an idea, rather than a long document or process, then we will. Analyze your audience before you make a presentation or conduct a meeting. Anticipate possible causes of confusion and prepare clarifying statements. As you prepare, try to see the situation from your audience's perspective. Give all the background necessary for people who receive your email, presentation or lecture to take action, such as make a decision based on the information you provide. If your topic requires a comprehensive understanding of complex underlying concepts, state so early in your discussion. Set clear expectations about what you hope your business communication can achieve. Choose the right communication format for each situation. For example, avoid using email to communicate emotional issues, such as bad news. Use written communication to convey lists of information, such as policies and procedures. Use diagrams and charts to summarize complicated financial data. Proofread your written communication, such as email, reports or other documents. Check for spelling and grammar mistakes so that you fix them before distributing your information. For email messages, include an effective subject line, discuss only one topic and specify the type of response you want. Pay attention to body language when communicating in person. A person who does not look at you or appears distracted in other ways may not be able grasp your message. Use physical cues to tailor your message or know when it might be appropriate to discuss the subject at another time. Defer judgment until the conversation concludes. Avoid interrupting the speaker with counter arguments. It limits your understanding of the situation. Recognize cultural differences in communication styles. Before you work with people from another country, take the time to investigate business practices in that area of the world.

(Reference:<https://smallbusiness.chron.com/achieve-success-through-effective-business-communication-2890.html>)

Visual Aids

Launch the PowerPoint Program

When you launch the PowerPoint program, you may be prompted to pick what kind of document you want to create. Choose to create a blank presentation.

Step: 1 Open the Power Point

Step:2 Create New Slide

Step:3 Making design

Step:4 Making Text

Step:5 Adding Picture on your Desktop Step:7 Save the Slide

Techniques for an Effective oral Presentation

While speaking to those we know about every day is a simple feat, it certainly requires adequate preparation and research to give a successful expression. The fourEs required for an effective speech have therefore been clarified for you below:

1. **Energy:** The introduction should be presented in an absolutely enthusiastic way that represents the strength. It helps to win over the audience and to make sure that you truly have everything to sell.
2. **Eye Contact:** Eye interaction with the listener is quite necessary. In case of broad assembly of audience start scanning from front to back as well as side to side. Any listener should get the feeling that you are engaging with them.
3. **Enthusiasm:** Your expression should represent your excitement and excitement for the topic you would be addressing. You should expect the same from the audience unless you are zealous about the subject.

4. **Examples:** Using illustrations always to demonstrate what you want to highlight. The listener often visualises what you are talking about because they don't look at words as text. Examples are the perfect way to help you create pictures of your post.

Video Marketing

It is no secret that video marketing is the future. Many companies, including Reebok and Always, have taken to video marketing to showcase their products and convey important messages. In fact, having a presence either on YouTube or video through Facebook is almost a necessity for most modern brands.

There are lots of things to remember when recording video for the first time. You'll need to consider:

- Having the right equipment (e.g. A tripod or camera)
- Having an appropriate filming location
- Using professional editing software
- Sourcing music

(Reference 1: Watch "A Moving Story about Gratitude" <https://youtu.be/tznztJVsW9E>)

(Reference 2: <https://www.slideshare.net/NicoleFerdinand/making-short-films>)

Basic script writing for the short film

Unique form

- Special order structure, emphasis, shape
- Fewer character emphasis and more systemic focus
- Too firm type - Punch line Joke movies?
- Non-verbal and surreal.
- Episodes

No Dialogue

- Action driven
- Little character development
- Potent set-up
- Gag & punch line

How to craft a great short film

- Conceive a brilliant, unusual, simple but intense idea
- Quickly establish your situation & characters
- Always start the story as late as possible & end it as soon as possible – it must be intense
- Always move the story forward
- Add a sense of urgency
- End with a bang Know your ending at the beginning
- Use dialogue sparingly
- Be brave in your choices
- Set it in your head, discuss it with your colleagues, redraft it, rewrite it, talk more about it, then storyboard it then make it

Don't try and cram too much in

Tell your own story or vision but be aware of other films in the same vein - allow yours to talk with them (GENRE)

- Three-act Structure - What this means? Give your story a beginning, middle, and end.

Don't write based on what you know. Use fantasy, your imagination & research

- You don't have to tell a story. You can focus on a theme, a state of mind, Experiment with an existing film or idea.
- If you make a genre film, fulfill the rules & then exceed them

Elements of Story

- The reason for telling the story
- Describing a need or a desire that must be addressed by the central character
- The reason for telling the story now for this audience
- Specific story/concept ANGLE

- Details through character & given circumstances
- Premise - insights - defining the goal of the story - the desired audience effect
(Example) King Lear - blind trust leads to destruction

Webisodes

- Web Series and Online Series
- WebTV - TV over IP - that is the real revolution to the temporary stop-gap of Cable. By being on-line and on-demand, TV over IP has no schedule restrictions
- 'WebTV' does not need the biggest audience; it just needs the Right audience, a dynamic and motivated and engaged audience.

Creating Web Page

A single disc, called the "html file" holds a web page. In virtually any software you would use to modify text files, html files can be generated. Also you can build html files in certain programmes. The value of these systems is that they are mostly user-friendly. The limitation is that the right html files are not always created. You will use the standard text editor, such as VI, PICO, Windows 95 Notepad etc to build web-pages. An html file includes control codes, which specify how a web viewer appears on the website. These codes are referred to as "html tags"

Password Protected Pages

There are many ways to build password-protected sites, but notice that using a CGI script is a typical vulnerability since the password is saved in a web server log file. Instead it is better to navigate, which is defined on a different tab.

Creating a Web Page

This is not meant as a full training course on designing web sites, it is intended to offer a deeper perspective into the fundamentals of making a web page. The easiest way to practice html coding is to open a certain html code on a website with a feature to meet your specifications and then change it.

Creating Blogs

A blog is a newspaper Web page that exists in reverse temporal sequences of the current entries first at the left, with the most previous. This is a forum for a writer or a community of authors to express their thoughts on a topic. More than 570 million blogs are now accessible on the internet. Bloggers are expected to cross 31.7 million by 2020 in the United States alone.

Purpose of a Blogs

- To improve the web site exposure in Google SERPs
- Helps to meet and catch interest from potential customers.
- The main goal of a blog is to bind with the community concerned.
- To improve your traffic and give your website quality.
- A blog is a valuable platform for lead generation.
- It creates trust in your followers as you utilize your niche expertise to produce insightful and entertaining content.

Steps to create a Blog

How to Start a Blog in 8 Easy Steps - Source : <https://firstsiteguide.com/start-blog/>

Step 1: Select a perfect niche for your blog

Step 2: Choose a blogging platform

Step 3: Pick a domain name

Step 4: Get a web hosting account

Step 5: Starting a blog on WordPress

Step 6: Select a theme and design your blog

Step 7: Write content and promote your blog

Step 8: Make money blogging

(Reference: <https://www.studiobinder.com/blog/writing-short-films/>)

Structure of Creating Blog

Blogs have modified their presence over time and nowadays blogs include a broad selection of posts and widgets. However some common functionality and frameworks do remain in most blogs. (Attributes: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZqZGKfd_qKc)

Features that a Typical Blog

- Menu header or browser bar.
- Highlighted or latest blog post Key Content Area.
- Facebook profile sidebar, desired material or call-to-action.
- Footer with links such as a disclosure, privacy policy, contact page etc.

Sample of Flyers

Business Management Flyers

(Source: <https://venngage.com/blog/flyer-examples/#1>)

Creation of Flyer

A flyer is a form of paper advertisement deliberate for wide supply and normally posted or distributed in a public place, handed out to individuals or sent through the mail. In the 2010s, flyers range from inexpensively photocopied leaflets to expensive, glossy, full-color circulars.

The various tips to be considered while creating the flyers;

1. Keep your content brief.
2. Divide your copy into digestible sections.
3. Use bullet points and infographics.
4. Create a catchy headline.
5. Add a call-to-action.
6. Don't forget to add directions.
7. Include your contact information
8. Always proofread your content
9. Communicate using your target market's language.
10. Use compelling testimonials.
11. Use colors that support your message.
12. Limit your font choices to two or three.
13. Choose the right paper stock
14. Apply paper coatings.
15. Use high-resolution photos

16. Incorporate your logo with the design
17. Account for bleed and trim
18. Distribute in high traffic areas

(Source: <https://www.nextdayflyers.com/blog/effective-business-flyers/>)

Uses of Flyers

- ✓ Advertise an event such as a music concert, nightclub appearance, festival, or political rally.
- ✓ Promote a goods-selling businesses such as a used car lot discount store or a service business such as a restaurant or massage parlor.
- ✓ Persuade people about a social, religious, or political message, as in evangelism or political campaign activities on behalf of a political party or candidate during an election. Flyers have been used in armed conflict: for example, airborne leaflet propaganda has been a tactic of psychological warfare.
- ✓ Recruit members for organizations or companies.

Like postcards, pamphlets and small posters, flyers are a low-cost form of mass marketing or communication.

Formats of flyer

- A4 (roughly letterhead size)
- A5 (roughly half letterhead size)
- DL (compliments slip size)
- A6 (postcard size)

Strategy and concept for the flyer

1. Find other flyers you like as inspiration

Look at other flyers outside to get an understanding of what is likely.

2. Use your design concept as a brief for a freelancer or design contest

You can either design your own flyer for you with your favorite freelancer or launch a flyer design competition and collect multiple flyer design suggestions from the world's designers.

3. Evaluate the design proposals against your criteria

Sort the prototypes without getting swept away by an innovative development that does not in reality accomplish what you need to do.

4. Choose your final design

Pick the template that better matches your needs and fits with your audience.

5. Proofread

Check and check again that no typos remain, until you have the completed design.

6. Make sure you get the files you need

If you have images as part of the template, the resolution must be high.

Brochure

A single or multi-page folded document used to advertise goods or services of a business is a brochure. This paper may be folded to make different pages or pages are piled together many times. In reference to a brochure, the word "booklet" is also used. Although it may appear identical to a brochure, brochures are most commonly used for ads of several goods or services for a business. It is important to remember. Usually brochures have more pictures than sentences. Such typical applications for brochures involve the launch or detailing of recent customer support contributions.

An overview of brochures

- Advertising products/services
- Sometimes binded
- Multiple pages

Difference between Brochure and Pamphlets

Brochure	Pamphlets
<ul style="list-style-type: none">❖ Usually consist of multiple bound pages❖ Paper size varies more than pamphlets❖ Cover a range of topics❖ Typically have pictures and graphics with supporting text❖ Good for informing readers about specific products or services and/or their features❖ Designed to sell rather than just educate or inform	<ul style="list-style-type: none">❖ Mostly printed on one folded page❖ May have more than one page, but not often❖ Most are not bound❖ The content focuses on a single subject❖ Usually more informational than promotional❖ Good for educating readers and raising awareness about a specific topic

Can you fill in the columns stated below based on the information given above:

Type	Purpose	Folded	Multiple Pages	Binded
Brochure				
Pamphlet				

Creating Brochures

Brand your brochure with visuals: You can add all your custom material, many photos, maps, icons and charts to your booklet of visual images. Incorporate the brand on a customised brochure or post photos of your own.

Add text: Submit text by inserting or substituting text in your brochure. The fonts, colours and sizes you may alter are easy

Add images: You will incorporate photos by adding symbols, portraits and stock images in our gallery, hundreds of thousands of images inserted into your brochure.

Publish and share: Make sure that you preview it when your brochure is final, you may also customize your printing brochure. You will share your creation with peers, acquaintances or relatives until you have your final draught.

Poster Making

A poster is a document depicting societal challenges and environmental issues. It could even be connected to certain commercials. It is essentially a work of art and because of its messages, draws maximum attention from the audience.

Importance of poster making

Poster presentations are a valid form of transferring academic knowledge. However, greater flexibility in their design and dissemination is required. 'MediaPoster' provides an opportunity to deliver a genuine depth of information, which is amendable to suit a wide variety of academic, professional and commercial disciplines. It accounts for a full range of learning styles by use of interactive delivery, and so promotes a genuine forum of active learning.

- Poster speaks for itself; the presence of its author is not necessary. It is therefore possible to reach a **broader audience** when compared to a presentation limited in time.
- It is also possible to **present several posters** in the same room and at the same time; visitors can have a look at those posters they are interested in.
- Sometimes as the author you have the possibility to present a poster while giving a short introduction. An **interactive situation evolves** while having a close contact to the audience, closer than when delivering a speech.
- Posters can be **used several times and presented at different events**.
- A poster is suited for people suffering from **stage fright at least**, for those who have difficulties when speaking in front of large groups. Standing next to their poster for some time in order to answer just a few questions is less stressful than talking on a lectern.

Format of Poster Writing

The students who are about to appear for the CBSE Board English examination must be aware of the format of poster making.

Format of poster writing

- **Issuing Authority:** Here you have to write the name of the organising body of the particular event.

- **Title:** This is the point where you can make the deal. Make a catchy title which is basically the gist of your announcement or issue.
- **A sketch:** After the title, you have a draw a picture depicting your issue. For instance; 4 ways to save water.
- **Date, Time and Venue:** Here you have to mention the date and time of the event which has to take place. Do not forget to mention the venue of the event.
- **Contact Information:** This is an important part of your poster. Remember to add the details of the concerned authorities as the people reading the poster must have contact numbers of the event co-ordinator in case any query arises on the day of the event.

Doing things for Poster Writing

- Your poster must not exceed the word limit of 50 words.
- The poster should be in a box.
- Make the content inside the poster to the point and crisp.
- Make sure your answer to a poster must fit in one page only. It should not be continued to the next page.
- Also, bold or underline the important information inside the poster.

Avoid things for Poster Writing

- Keep the word limit within the prescribed word limit only.
- Do not use complex language.
- Do not use the short form of the words.
- Make sure your poster is in the proper structure / format.

Sample Poster

**A Novel Approach to Campus Health and Wellness:
The UCLA Healthy Campus Initiative**

Tyler D. Watson, MPH¹ and Ryan Babadi, MPH²

Live Well is a campus-wide wellness movement with the goal of making UCLA the healthiest university campus in America.
<http://healthy.ucla.edu/>

CAMPUS POPULATION	STRUCTURE	CHALLENGES AND SUCCESSES
<p>Live Well includes the entire campus community:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~4,000 faculty ~26,000 staff ~42,000 students ~200 buildings = 17 million ft² built space 419 acres (0.66mi²); smallest UC campus 	<p>EAT WELL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community Gardens Healthy Beverages Food Literacy Healthy Vending <p>BE WELL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web Presence and Social Media: managed by graduate student researcher Active Transportation Stairwell Activation Campus Safety Tour de UCLA Bike Ride <p>MIND WELL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> UC Global Food Initiative: implementation of food and nutrition academic programs Wellness Apps + "U-Reviews" Stress and Resiliency Assessment Sleep Well campaign Mindfulness Programming The Happiness Challenge <p>MOVE WELL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Health Champions Active Meetings/Instant Recess Movement Research Courses Dance Events/Experiences <p>BREATHE WELL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tobacco-Free Campus Policy Tobacco Cessation Resources E-cigarettes Inclusion in Policy 	<p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cross-campus coordination of large groups Branding and recognition Student turnover and leadership transition Large and diverse campus population Wide range of health disparities <p>Successes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bringing together diverse health groups Practical, action-based projects New data collection and publications Impact beyond the UCLA campus UC President Napolitano recommendation for a Live Well model at all UC campuses
<p>CORE VALUES</p> <p>A "healthy campus" is a place that:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fosters high-level wellness 2. Encourages personal responsibility 3. Respects diversity 4. Strives to reduce inequalities in health 5. Is integrative 	<p>PROCESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support and integrate existing health-related groups, programs, and activities • Use best practices to coordinate new approaches and programs • Map campus assets and learn from different stakeholders • Organize community collaborations and facilitate bottom-up approaches • Host monthly steering committee meetings and area-specific working groups • Fund and facilitate student projects related to Live Well goals and values • Develop metrics to measure health and wellness changes • Maintain a website and other campus communications for resources and events 	<p>KEYS TO SUCCESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizational integration • Administration buy-in • Interdisciplinary leadership • Including non-traditional stakeholders • Targeted and adaptable use of resources • Combination of research and practice • Collaboration between pods • Graduate student researcher input • FUN!
	<p>ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS</p> <p>UCLA Healthy Campus Initiative is envisioned and supported by Jane and Terry Serniel. A special thank you to Live Well leadership including Dr. Wendy Slusser, Dr. Michael Goldstein, Louise Ino, pod leaders and graduate student researchers, and steering committee members.</p>	

Sample of conference poster presentation

(Source: <http://dmst.aueb.gr/dds/rese/poster/indexw.htm>)

Writing Slogan

A slogan is a term that describes a commodity or a business and expresses the main advantage to customers. And if carefully planned, the brand will hold the mind of customers on the front and centre until they are ready to purchase.

Seven tips to creative juices flowing:

- Keep it short and simple
- Be consistent
- Focus on what makes you different
- Make it timeless
- Ensure it can stand alone
- Consider your target market
- Get input

Captions Making

A title, brief summary, or a picture or illustration accompanying with one particular thing may be product or service. A collection of terms on the bottom of the TV or the movie frame of the Convey conversation, or adapt international conversation to hearing disabled people. As of a text or document: a name or a portion. Law The heading, court, words and the number of the proceeding, of a pleading or other text. While a thousand words worth an image, it also takes a picture to attract viewers, have a backdrop and illustrate the plot.

Tips for writing effective captions

- A headline, a concise description, or a corresponding image or diagram.
- A list of words at the base of the television or the theatre
- Transmit dialogue or tailor conversation to those with hearing impairments worldwide.
- The heading of the proceedings, session, terms and amount of a pleading or other document.
- Although a picture is worth a thousand words, it often requires a photo to depict audiences, have a history and explain the storyline.

Tips for writing better Instagram captions.

1. Write several drafts first.
2. Front-load the important stuff.
3. Include a call-to-action.
4. Limit yourself to four hashtags.
5. Meld your brand voice with Instagram's lighthearted tone.
6. Use emojis.
7. Cross-promote your other social channels.
8. When in doubt, keep it brief.

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Unit – 5

UNIT - 5

WORKPLACE COMMUNICATION – AN OVERVIEW

Clear and effective communication is essential in a workplace. Although there are various channels of communication such as E-mail, circulars, WhatsApp etc. a lack of effective communication will end in misunderstanding with the boss, co-workers, or colleagues. This will bring down productivity as it may result in a breakdown of communication and therefore relationships. Effective communication is the art of saying the right words in the right way at the right time. This will lead to improving confidence and a positivity ultimately leading to career growth.

Leaders need to recognise the importance of having strong internal communications in their organizations. Leaders also need to recognize the importance of formal communication channels within the organization. This will keep the organization glued together and move towards one unified goal and purpose. This communication between leaders and their teams, or between team members, keeps employees informed of important changes in the organization. It also provides them an outlet to share their own thoughts.

The methods of Communication

(Image source: WikiHow: How to write an Internal Communication Plan)

List methods of communication

Passive Channels:

- Intranet news
- TV
- Notice boards
- Email
- Posters
- Print

Interactive Channels:

- Company conference
- Business unit briefing
- Blogs
- Discussion Forums
- Instant Messaging
- face to face meetings

Tips for effective communication in workplace:

1. Speak clearly and assertively
2. Listen to your co-workers
3. Ensure accuracy to build trust
4. Share information that's specific and detail oriented
5. Keep your communications brief
6. Follow up important conversations in writing
7. Don't hesitate to ask for clarification
8. Ditch the electronics before and during in-person meetings
9. Make a list of your strengths and weaknesses
10. Learn from your mistakes.

1. WARM UPEXERCISES

1. Career Vocabulary Grid

The following words are related to career. Rearrange the letters to form meaningful words. Write down the words in the space provided on the next page. Also, match the words with the definitions by writing the number in the circles.

01

c	n
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02

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03

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me	

04

a	a
c	v
ncy	

05

k	r
w	o
force	

06

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d	o
s1z1ng	

7

i	c
e	n
ntives	

8

m	r
o	p
otion	

9

a	a
l	s
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10

e	i
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gn	

11

t	n
e	i
rv1ew	

12

r	p
P	a
entice	

No.Rearrangedwords

Roughwork

- 01.
- 02.
- 03.
- 04.
- 05.
- 06.
- 07.
- 08.
- 09.
- 10.
- 11.
- 12.

Lr. No. Definitions

- A. Reduction in the number of people who work in a company to reduce expenses.
- B. money that employees receive in the beginning of every month for doing their job.
- C. that which is given to encourage workers to do more work.
- D. A regular increase in the amount of money that the workers are paid for their job.
- E. a job that is available for somebody to do.
- F. to officially tell the authorities that one is leaving one's job.
- G. needing a lot of skill, patience, and effort.
- H. a summary of academic-cum-work history.
- I. a formal meeting at which somebody is asked questions to see if they are suitable for a particular job or position.
- J. A person who works for a fixed period to learn the skills needed in the job.
- K. a move to a more important job or rank in a company.
- L. all those who work for a particular company.

Source: Joy, John Love J & Francis M. Peter S. J, Let's communicate 2 – An ESL textbook – cum-workbook for college students. Delhi: Trinity Press, 2016.

2. People at work - who's who

Given below are job-related words / abbreviations. Go through the list and match the words with their descriptions given on the following page by writing their letters in the appropriate boxes

Word list

- | | | |
|----------------|-----------------|---------------|
| a. engineer | k. video-jockey | u. farmer |
| b. programmer | l. manager | v. butcher |
| c. cashier | m. peon | w. waiter |
| d. professor | n. receptionist | x. accountant |
| e. umpire | o. Doctor | y. broker |
| f. ambassador | p. mechanic | z. athlete |
| g. typist | q. employee | a1. chef |
| h. electrician | r. plumber | b1. vendor |
| l. advocate | s. carpenter | c1. mason |
| j. tailor | t. merchant | d1. employer |

No. Meanings:

1. Receives and pays out money in a bank/company
2. Deals with people arriving at or telephoning a hotel
3. Serves customers at their tables in a restaurant
4. Lives in a foreign country as a senior representative
5. Is a university teacher of the highest rank
6. makes sure that rules are not broken in a game
7. Presents programmes on TV channels
8. Repairs engines of motor vehicles
9. Uses scientific knowledge to solve practical problems
10. Keeps or checks financial accounts
11. One who types letters, memos etc.
12. Writes programs for computers
13. Treats people who are ill or injured
14. Pays the employers to work for them
15. Cultivates and manages land
16. Kills animals and sells them as meat in a shop
17. Competes in sports such as running, jumping
18. Sells things usually on the street
19. Defends somebody in a court of law
20. Oversees running a business
21. Fits and repairs things such as water pipes, toilets
22. Makes or repairs wooden objects and structures
23. Connects or repairs electrical equipment
24. Does mostly physical work like carrying files etc.
25. Builds or works with stone
26. A professional head-cook in a restaurant
27. Buys and sells goods in large quantities
28. Is paid to work for somebody
29. Buys/sells for another in exchange for a commission
30. Makes suit, jackets for individual custom

Source: Joy, John Love J & Francis M. Peter S. J, Let's communicate 2 – An ESL textbook – cum-workbook for college students. Delhi: Trinity Press, 2016.

SPEAKING SKILLS

Academic Power Point Presentation

Pre-text task – Vocabulary

<i>brainstem</i>	<i>potential explanation</i>
<i>data collection</i>	<i>clip arts</i>
<i>parameters</i>	<i>video clips</i>
<i>quantitative analysis</i>	

Power Point Presentations have come into vogue more than a decade ago. Not only in educational institutions, but in business scenario also it has established its importance. Yet, for the students who do the presentation for the first time, there occurs a fear in them to speak before a large gathering. This article guides the students to overcome their fear and to take up the task actively and enthusiastically.

Before preparing the presentation, it is important to decide what the main message is going to be. This central idea is the core around which all other ideas revolve. For instance, in academic presentations the central idea will be the thesis statement, in business presentation it will be the product or services offered. In any case the content must be prepared before the power point presentation.

Plan the structure of your Power Point Presentation

Now that you know what information must be included, begin to plan the structure of your presentation. You will want to plan as much of your speech and slides on paper as possible. Outline not only your speech but your slides as well.

- The structure of an academic presentation should follow roughly the same structure as an academic paper, first introducing your main point, supporting it with evidence, and then a short conclusion.
- For business presentations, Guy Kawasaki (a notable business adviser and marketing guru) suggests this standard presentation structure:
 - The Problem
 - Your solution
 - Business model
 - Underlying magic/technology
 - Marketing and sales
 - Competition
 - Team
 - Projections and milestones
 - Status and timeline
 - Summary and call to action

- Future

Making PPT effective:

1. Write out your speech before you start making the PowerPoint:

It's hard to make a presentation if you don't know what you plan to say. Brainstorm what you plan to say and break it into chunks. Then, make an outline or jot down notes for yourself. You might even create a short script.

2. Use your outline or notes to help you decide what needs to be included in your slides.

The following points may be considered for academic presentation:

- Introduction or Overview
- Theoretical Framework or Research Question
- Background or Literature Review
- Background or Literature Review
- Methodology or Case Selection
- Discussion of Data or Results
- Analysis
- Conclusion

The outline structure of a presentation resembles the structure of a research work. Academic presentation always aims or focuses on some finding or innovation. Make your presentation also creative and informative.

3. Be informative and innovative

In the presentation, refer to the existing literature and give background information on a particular case with which the audience may be familiar. Your background information should only include what is expected or needed by the audience. In your 15-minute presentation, after formal introduction and literature, you need to be discussing your data or case study. At conferences, people are there to learn about your unique contribution and not about another person's work. In some places you can narrate your experiences in collecting data. Add humor, wherever necessary, to avoid sounding monotonous.

4. Rehearse:

Take rehearsal as you need before you deliver your presentation. Practicing makes it flow better. You can't practice too many times. Prepare your material according to the time allotted for you. No more. Even if you only have a few minutes left, you need to finish within the allotted time.

5. Use Photos, Pictures and graphs:

You can use pie charts, graphs or bar charts when discussing any quantitative analysis. Also, use photos, pictures, videos, music, and clip arts wherever necessary. Sometime pictorial explanation reaches the audience with ease. Relevant video clips can also be used to make the session lively.

At the end, give a recap of all the points that you had explained in your presentation.

6. Challenges:

Be assertive in your tone while delivering the material. Never get distracted from your focus on speaking out the content. While rehearsing, think of the possible questions that may be thrown to you regarding the subject and you should be prepared to answer everything.

Points to be avoided in a Power Point Presentation

1. Don't overload materials:

Avoid presenting all the information in one slide. Overloading a slide with too much information will tend to give a cumbersome appearance. Limit content to bullet points.

2. Limit the number of slides:

Keep minimum number of slides to make your presentation effective. Too many slides would make the audience weary of it and they may tend to get distracted

3. Do not read the slides:

Always keep eye contact with the audience. While doing the presentation, don't read from the slides, instead, you can keep flash cards, or a printout of your presentation.

4. Use professional format:

Make your slides captivating and innovative. Don't use visuals that distract the attention of the audience from the topic. Don't use multiple fonts. Stick to a particular readable font throughout the presentation.

Consider the following sample presentation. Observe its structure and outline your own presentation. Explain the outline to the class.

Sample Power Point Presentation no.1

(Source: Dr. Saravanadevi R. Associate professor & Head of Dept of Management, GAC, Kumarapalaym, Erode, Tamil Nadu)

HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

- > MEANING
- > SCOPE
- > NEED
- > FUNCTIONS

MEANING

- Human Resource Development is the framework of helping employees develop their skills, knowledge and abilities, which in turn improves an organization's effectiveness. Find out what types of activities are part of human resource development and the benefits it can have for an organization.

MEANING

- The function of human resource development is to improve performance and ability. Regardless of the form the development takes, it functions as a means to improve the overall performance and ability of employees in the jobs they are doing and in future positions.

SCOPE OF HRD

HRD INCLUDES.....

- Employee Orientation
- Staff Training
- Career Development And
- Management Development

NEED FOR HRD

- Changes in Economic Policies
- Changing Job Requirements
- Need for Multi-skilled Human Resources
- Organisational Viability & Transformation Process
- Technological Advancements
- Organisational Complexity
- Maintain Good Human Relations

FUNCTIONS OF HRD....

- > Organisational change and organisational development
- > Involvement in social and religious organisations, quality circles and workers' participation in decision making.

Sample Power Point Presentation No.2

The topic of this presentation is Free Consent in Commercial law. As students of Commerce & Management you may be expected to design your presentation after this model. Read carefully and learn to make your subject presentation at its best!

(Source: Dr. Hema A.S. Asst. professor of Commerce, GAC(W), Salem, Tamil Nadu)

COMMERCIAL LAW

FREE CONSENT

FREE CONSENT

According to Sec 12 of the Indian Contract Act one of the essentials of a valid contract is "Free Consent"

Sec 13 defines "consent" as "Two or more persons are said to consent when they agree upon the same thing in the same sense".

According to Sec 14, consent is said to be free when it is not caused by:

- 1.Coercion
- 2.Undue influence
- 3.Fraud
- 4.Misrepresentation
- 5.Mistake

COERCION

According to Sec 15 coercion means "Committing or threatening to commit any act forbidden by Indian Penal Code 1860 or unlawful detaining or threatening to detain any other persons property with a view to enter into an agreement. It is immaterial whether the IPC is or is not in force where the coercion is employed"

The threat amounting to coercion need not necessarily be from a party to contract, it may also proceed from a stranger to the contract.

Consent is said to be caused by coercion when obtained by:

- 1.The committing or threatening to commit any act forbidden by the Indian Penal Code
- 2.The unlawful detaining or threatening to detain any property

It is not important whether the IPC is or not in force where the coercion is taking place.

For example, A and B, Britishians are on a voyage trip to America. A says to B, "Come with me into the Atlantic Ocean. If you refuse, I will shoot you into the water". Although the IPC is not in force on the Atlantic Ocean it is still considered a coercion.

Important cases:

- 1.Chikkai Ammappa vs Seshamma.

In this case a person threatened his wife and son that he would suicide if she doesn't transfer her property in his brother's favour. The wife and son executed the release of the deed under the threat. Held the threat of suicide amounted to coercion within Sec 15 and the release deed was therefore voidable.

This also is a very important case to prove that threat to commit suicide amounts to coercion

2. Ranganayakamma vs. Alwar Setty;

A young widowed girl of 13 years was forced to adopt a boy by her relatives who prevented the removal of his body for cremation until she consented. Held the consent was not free but was induced by coercion. Consequently the adoption was set aside.

3. Muthia vs. Muthu Karuppa:

An agent refused to hand over the account books of a business to the new agent unless the principal released him from all liabilities, the principal had to give a release deed. Held the deed was given under coercion and was voidable at the option of the principal.

4. Bansraj vs. Secretary of State:

The government gave a threat of attachment against the property of P for the recovery of the fine due from his son. P paid the fine. Held contract was induced by coercion

UNDUE INFLUENCE

Sometimes a party is compelled to enter into a contract against his will as a result of unfair persuasion by the other party.

Section 16 defines undue influence as follows A contract is said to be induced by "undue influence" where the relations subsisting between the parties are such that one of the parties is in a position to dominate the will of the other and uses that position to obtain an unfair advantage over the other

Essentials of undue influence

1. There are two persons
2. The relations are satisfying between them
3. One must dominate the other
4. There must be unfair advantage
5. It involves the moral pressure

There is an undue influence between the following persons:

- Principal and agent
- Superior and subordinate
- Doctor and patient
- Father and son
- Teacher and student
- Promoter and company
- Master servant
- Spiritual advisor and devotee

Among the following relations there is no undue influence

- 1.wife and husband
- 2.landlord and tenant
- 3.laborer and creditor

CASE: Raniammapparna vs. Sorninathan

A poor Hindu widow was persuaded by a money lender to agree to pay 100% rate of interest on money lent by him. She needed the money to establish her right to maintenance. It was a clear case of undue influence and the court reduced the rate of interest to 24%

FRAUD

According to Sec 17 fraud means and includes any of those acts committed by a party to contract or with his connivance or by his agent with an intent to deceive or induce a person to enter a contract:

1. The suggestion that a fact is true when it is not true and the person making it does not believe in its truth
2. The active concealment of a fact by a person having knowledge or belief of the fact
3. A promise made without any intention of performing it
4. Any other act fitted to deceive
5. Any such act or omission as the law specially declares to be fraudulent

The essentials of fraud are:

1. There must be a representation or assertion and it must be false
2. The representation must relate to a fact
3. The representation must have been made with the intention of inducing the other party to act upon it
4. the representation must have been made with a knowledge of its falsity
5. the other party must have subsequently suffered some loss

MISREPRESENTATION

According to Sec 18 there is misrepresentation:

1. When a person positively asserts a fact is true when his information does not warrant it to be so, though he believes it to be true
2. When there is any Breach of duty by a person which brings an advantage to the person committing it by misleading another to his prejudice
3. When a party causes however innocently the other party to the agreement to make a mistake as to the substance of the thing which is the subject of the agreement

Important case:

Babel vs. R.A.Singh:

M was a marriage broker who gave Y the photograph of a man and told him that the man was young and rich. Y conveyed the same to his daughter who agreed for the proposal. But on the day of marriage it was discovered that the man was the age of 60. There is fraud between M and Y, whereas there is misrepresentation between Y and his daughter.

MISTAKE

```

graph TD
    Mistake --> Mistake_of_law[Mistake of law]
    Mistake --> Mistake_of_fact[Mistake of fact]
    Mistake_of_law --> Of_the_foreign_country[Of the foreign country]
    Mistake_of_law --> Of_the_home_country[Of the home country]
    Mistake_of_fact --> Bilateral_mistake[Bilateral mistake]
    Mistake_of_fact --> Unilateral_mistake[Unilateral mistake]
    Unilateral_mistake --> Mistake_as_to_subject_matter[Mistake as to subject matter]
    Unilateral_mistake --> Mistake_as_to_person[Mistake as to person]
    Unilateral_mistake --> Mistake_as_to_attribute[Mistake as to attribute]
    Mistake_as_to_subject_matter --> Physical_impossibility[Physical impossibility]
    Mistake_as_to_subject_matter --> Legal_impossibility[Legal impossibility]
    Physical_impossibility --> existence[existence]
    Physical_impossibility --> identity[identity]
    Physical_impossibility --> quality[quality]
    Physical_impossibility --> quantity[quantity]
    Legal_impossibility --> life[life]
    Legal_impossibility --> price[price]
  
```

The above two sample presentations are provided in text format. Now, you will get a visual presentation by clicking the link given: <https://youtu.be/0srjdRDh99Y>

It is a presentation hosted by Jim Riley on YouTube. The topic is Marketing: Segmentation – Targeting and Positioning. Listen to the video presentation attentively and enhance your knowledge of designing such presentations in your subject as well as workplaces too. At the end of this unit, you will be asked questions related to this video presentation.

Post reading Task I

Answer the following in about 30 words each:

1. Give the structure of a business presentation.
2. Write the formula of an academic presentation.
3. Why should the content be informative and innovative?
4. What are the challenges that you might face while doing a presentation?
5. What is the necessity to rehearse before doing a presentation?

Task II

With the help of the sample presentations provided in the text, prepare your own presentation on any topic of your interest, and present it in your class.

Task III

After listening to the video hosted by Jim Riley, on Marketing - Segmentation- Targeting and positioning, answer the following questions in about 30 words.

1. What is market segmentation? Mention its main categories.
2. Write about the benefits of effective market segmentation.
3. Explain the drawbacks of market segmentation.
4. What are target markets and its main strategies?
5. Explain market positioning with examples.

Task IV

Form groups of five among your classmates and discuss the following topics. Prepare essays adding your own ideas also.

1. Positioning and competitive advantage
2. Possible positioning strategies

READING AND WRITING SKILLS

1. Product Profile

PRE-TEXT TASK – VOCABULARY

<i>reputation</i>	<i>trustworthiness</i>
<i>marketing</i>	<i>credentials</i>
<i>indispensable</i>	<i>surveillance</i>
<i>robust</i>	<i>sustainable</i>

A company profile is a short piece of writing which introduces the company to someone who might be unfamiliar with it. The purpose of a product profile is to furnish basic information about the company, its products, product description, performance, reputation, etc. When a product is aimed at selling, online or offline, one of the key factors is the product description. In business, a product sale depends on advertising and marketing department's way in promoting the sale.

Product Description:

While describing a product, the following points are to be noted:

1. Target audience
 - The target audience to whom the product is to be sold and their buying capacity, location, and literacy level.
 - If the company has an online access, a team can be appointed to monitor and gather the information of the people who visit the company's website. An online enquiry form may be provided to identify their demographic using Google Analytics.
 - When a new brand of a product is to be introduced in the market, try to connect your item to the target customer's lifestyle and utility.
2. Features of the product
 - Design a list of the benefits of the products and link these to the customers' needs.
 - Explain the exceptional features of the product
3. Appeal to the senses
 - Specifics are important in selling a product. So, creating an imaginary sensory experience of using the product is important.

Sample Product Profile

Read the fictitious profile given below:

Sunshine Enterprises is a domestic lighting and security provider established in 1989. We have considerable expertise in sustainable lighting including solar lighting. Our company is reputed nationwide for its products and services. Our products are recognized and trusted across the world. Our company recruits employees in large scale every year to manage the production.

A brief Profile of the company:

Type	Public
Purpose	Lifestyle (safety & security)
Established	1989
Founder	Mr. Sharma
Headquarters	Bangalore
Area covered	India
Products	LED lights Solar lights Surveillance cameras
Credentials	ISO certified
Website	sunshineco.in

Product Profile

Name of the product: Sunbeam LED lighting integrated security camera

Product Description:

We believe that proper lighting and security are essential for every house. With this in mind, we have developed a Sunbeam LED lighting system integrated with security system that is efficient, economical, and eco-friendly. Soon, we hope to be patented for this new product. Nowadays, providing adequate security and surveillance to houses has become indispensable need for everyone. Sunbeam knocks out the need for a separate security camera network by compacting surveillance with lighting. Using inbuilt cameras and wireless cloud technology, the Sunbeam system can be used to set up a site-wide security system which can be monitored locally or remotely.

Our products are highly customizable and we have a dedicated team to provide prompt service to any part of the country. We are committed to the society and to the environment. All our factories and offices are exclusively for sustainable energy sources and our products are certified as recyclable.

(Source: Google images: CCTV camera with LED lights)

Robust features:

- Solar energy supply, recyclable, and power saving
- Bullet camera with stylish and unique design
- Built-in 8 pcs LED lights to provide adequate lighting even in heavy darkness
- Metal case, IP65 waterproof
- 90-degree rotation solar panel

Both the models are white in color, made of lithium battery, rechargeable, and replaceable. Our products are ISO certified. Both are waterproofed and weather proofed. The company aims at upgrading the existing models to attract worldwide customers. It plans to start its branches in a few more cities of other states.

Perception:

This profile establishes the trustworthiness of the company by stating that it has been in operation for seventy years. The main products and services offered by the company are also introduced here. The credential of the company being ISO certified is also mentioned. The best practices one of which is their commitment to environmental issues, is also pointed out. The profile closes with a brief outline of the company's objectives and future directions. This indicates that the company is eager to achieve more in its field.

Post-reading task – 1

1. Enumerate the components mentioned in Sunshine Enterprises' (SE) profile?
2. What are the special features of the Sunbeam LED lighting integrated security camera?
3. Mention the robust features of the specified product.
4. How do you know that the SE is committed to the environment?
5. Write a note on the points to remember while describing a company product.

Task – 2

Design a profile for a brand-new coffee product of your desired company. Compare your profile with other groups.

READING and WRITING

2. Writing a Circular

PRE-TEXT TASK	VOCABULARY
<i>luncheons</i>	<i>implement</i>
<i>intimating</i>	<i>informative</i>
<i>adhere</i>	<i>geared</i>
<i>queries</i>	<i>stake</i>

Circulars or fliers are an effective way to communicate in an organization. In general, companies, organizations or even educational institutions use circulars to implement policies or invite employees to meetings or sometimes to luncheons. Circulars can also be used to promote new products. Circulars are written to inform the stake holders the matters of general interest. Circulars serve a lot of benefits to both the sender and the receiver. The success of a circular in business communication depends on its distribution.

Advantages of Circulars:

Circular is the fastest way to pass information among the stake holders in an organization or a company, whether it is in printed form or digital form. Circulars enable the efficient transfer of information. For example, a company needs only a few lines of subject to inform employees about a seminar.

Circulars aimed at specific target group are highly effective. For example, a circular inviting the company stake holders or specific department's employees to learn database management is geared toward marketing research managers and computer programmers. If the company or organization publishes its own newsletter, circulars can be made to appear in them, for those who did not receive them on the specific date. Circulars are inexpensive and timely in delivering or conveying the intended messages.

A Circular identifies the right audience as it has a wider dimension and reach. It can be referred to as a legal document with the designation of authority and therefore acts as a permanent record.

Key features to make an effective Circular:

1. A Circular is a small piece of business, professional or organizational communication made with the purpose of intimating important or urgent information to be conveyed to its stakeholders.
2. It is normally sent by the company/ organization managers or head of the office.
3. Circular can be inter-departmental or inter-office depending on the need to be sent and the number of people involved in it.
4. The sender is expected to be very clear with the messages to be conveyed to the target group.
5. A circular should contain all the information about the subject to be conveyed.
6. When a circular is meant to promote a product, the company can use catchy captions to attract the readers.
7. A circular is sent to a wider audience and is a formal circulation. Therefore, care should be taken to avoid any ambiguously.

(Image Source: WikiHow: How to write a Circular Letter)

Here is a sample circular of a company to inform the revised working days:

ABC Company

Circular no. 15

Date:19.8.2020

Revised working days

Dear employees of ABC company,

This is to inform you all that there will be a change in the working days of our company. So far, we have been working from Monday to Friday (only 5 working days in a week) with the working hours of 9.00 a.m. to 5.00 p.m. It is felt necessary to revise or increase the working days by adding Saturday as a working day, without altering the existing working hours. The need had occurred due to the loss of working days we met due to the pandemic situation. Hope everyone understands the need of the hour and will extend your cooperation without compromising on the quality of work. The revised working days will be as follows:

- Working days: Monday to Saturday (except holidays)
- Working time: 9.00 a.m. to 5.00p.m.

All employees are requested to take a note of this change which will come into effect from this Saturday i.e., 22.08.2020. You are requested to strictly adhere to the revised working days and defaulters will be subjected to action. Kindly contact the HR department to address your queries.

Thanks!

CEO

ABC Company.

Post reading tasks:

1. Imagine yourself as a HR manager of Sun Technologies. Send a circular to your employees asking them to assemble for a meeting to discuss about the upcoming auditing in the company. Write in 200words.
2. Answer the following in about 30 words each:
 1. What is a flyer?
 2. To whom is the circular sent?
 3. Who drafts the circular?
 4. What is the purpose of a business circular?
 5. Why should a circular be objective?
3. In about 100 words write about the advantages of sending a circular.

READING and WRITING

3. Writing minutes of a meeting

PRE-TEXT TASK - VOCABULARY

<i>disputes</i>	<i>dissenting</i>
<i>reliable</i>	<i>enumerated</i>
<i>unbiased</i>	<i>freebies</i>
<i>unambiguous</i>	<i>agenda</i>
<i>prudent</i>	<i>abstention</i>

Minutes of a meeting are record of documented proceedings of discussed issues in a meeting. It includes the decisions taken and the action plan which needs to be recorded soon after the meeting. While writing the minutes one must be careful in documenting what transpired during the meeting, since they become authentic evidence. In some legal disputes, minutes can serve as a reliable document. The person deputed to draft the minutes should take down hints or notes during the meeting so as not to overlook even small issues discussed in the meeting. The minutes serve as a useful reference for anyone who was unable to attend the meeting. So, the minutes of a meeting also serve as a reference material for the future.

The following are some points to be noted to make the minutes of a meeting reliable and trustworthy:

- The minutes should be written objectively and in an unbiased manner using clear language to avoid ambiguity
- It is prudent avoid using abbreviations and excessive technical terms to enable the readers to understand the concepts easily
- It is desirable to not mention the name of a particular member while writing about the discussion on a particular subject (unless it is necessary for future reference). It is enough to record only the happenings and resolutions made at the meeting and avoid mentioning who caused that action.
- The minutes should be written immediately after the meeting to avoid omission of any relevant points.
- All the events or happenings should be recorded in the order they occurred.
- If any member needs any correction to be made in the minutes of a previous meeting, with the consent from all members, it can be carried out in the minutes of the current meeting with necessary adjustments to the minutes of the previous meeting under consideration.

The structure of the minutes:

The minutes of a meeting typically comprises of the following components:

- Date, time, and place of the meeting
- Names of those present
- Names of those unable to attend
- Topics discussed
- Members opinions or suggestions
- Any dissenting
- Decisions arrived
- Action plan
- Tentative date of next meeting
- Distribution of the minutes to those present and getting it signed

(Image source: WikiHow: How to Take Minutes)

The minutes, thus, become a recorded document of the important decisions taken, and methods and motions adopted in a company or organization.

Sample minutes of a meeting in an organization:

RAINBOW MALL

MINUTES OF THE EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE MEETING

Day & Date: Wednesday, 14th October 2020

Time: 4.00 p.m.

Place: Executive Conference Room, Hotel Ashoka, Chennai

Present: Mr. Gupta - Chairman

The following Executive Committee members:

Mr. Narain Das

Mr. Ravirajan

Ms. Deepti

Ms. Kalpana

Mr. Raghav

Mr. Ashok

In attendance

Mr. Ajit, Secretary

Ms. Abhinaya Sri, PRO

Apologies:

Mr. Khanna

Ms. Suji

The Chair welcomed members to the meeting. Draft Minutes of the Meeting:

Minutes no.1

Motion: Confirmation of the previous meeting minutes.

Decision: The minutes of the previous meeting were approved as an accurate record with the consent of the members present.

Minutes no.2

Motion: Appointing a HR manager at Trichy branch, proposed by Mr. Karthik

Decision: Mr. Karthik presented the details of the interview conducted for the post of HR manager for Trichy branch along with the recommendations of the interview panel.

It was accepted to appoint Mr. Arun to this post.

Minutes no.3

Motion: Constructing a children's park near the car parking area, proposed by Mr. Sathish

Decision: The members discussed the pros and cons of such a park. Mr. Sathish, one of the EC members enumerated the benefits of children's park in a shopping mall and explained the members that such an idea would enhance the sales in all shops, as it would allow parents to shop freely. The proposal was accepted as a positive step for the growth of the mall.

Minutes no.4

Motion: Announcement of freebies and offers during festival times, proposed by Mr. Shiva

Decision: The committee decided to announce freebies and offers for the upcoming festivals. The items to be given as freebies and the amount of offer were also discussed and finalised.

Minutes no.5

Motion: Date of next meeting

Decision: It was decided to meet after a fortnight and the meeting was adjourned.

Writing Corporate minutes

Corporate minutes of shareholders meeting or directors' meetings are mandated by law. These minutes may be referred to when there are lawsuits and key information is required. Therefore, detailed notes must be taken in corporate minutes. Also, it is required to complete the minutes immediately and obtain approval from the board.

Tips to write corporate minutes effectively:

1. Note details about the meeting. Before the meeting starts note down the following details:

- full name of your company
- date and time of the meeting
- location of the meeting

2. Write down who attends. Make a list of those members attending and those not attending the meeting. Include any guests or consultants who have been invited.

- Note any late arrivals or the time when someone leaves the meeting early.
- Also write down who is conducting the meeting and whether a quorum was present.

3. Record the meeting's purpose:

A meeting's purpose may be varied. They are as follows:

- annual meeting for directors and shareholders
- meeting to determine employee hiring
- meeting to discuss compensation
- announcement of new officers
- issue stock
- discussion of financial activity, such as a new bank or line of credit

4. Note whether prior minutes were accepted. The minutes of the previous meeting should have been distributed to the members in advance. The first motion will be to confirm the business arising from the previous meeting. Write down the vote.

- If someone objects to the minutes, discussion may ensue. Make a note of the discussion and the changes to be made.

5. Take notes of discussion on agenda items. Detailed notes on the discussions should be taken down. Words should be accurately recorded. Active listening is very important.

- Avoid trying to take down a word-for-word transcription. If for instance a person opposes a point and explains why for a long time, it is sufficient to note that the point was opposed and to state the reason.

- Note what documents the attendees are looking at. All documents that are circulated among the attendees should be noted and a copy of the same should be attached with the minutes.

6. Record the vote on items. If voting is included as a part of the agenda, it must be recorded in the minutes along with the details of those who are absent and who decline to vote.

- Generally, most resolutions will be adopted unanimously. However, the names of dissenters should be recorded. This is very important.
- For example, you can write: "Resolution adopted. Dissent: Raja. Abstention: Amuldas, Vakrie."

7. Record the adjournment. The time the meeting is adjourned should also be recorded. If the schedule for the next meeting is decided that also should be noted.

- For example, you can write, “The next meeting was scheduled for July 1, 2016, time and place to be determined. The meeting adjourned at 6:16pm.”

8. Type the minutes as soon as possible: You might have taken handwritten notes while sitting in the meeting. As soon as the meeting is over type out the minutes so that you will remember the essence of the proceedings.

9. Circulate your draft minutes. Your draft needs to be reviewed. Follow your corporation’s policy. You might need to produce your draft to the higher authorities in the management who would take a call regarding the minutes. The minutes may be modified as per the recommendations from the head of the management such as the CEO, the CFO etc.

- You may then need to distribute the draft to a broader group of management, which may also have comments.
- Finally, you will distribute the minutes to the full board since they will be voting on the minutes for the next meeting.

10. Store your approved minutes: You don’t have to file your corporate minutes with your state. Minutes should be documented carefully and stored for future references at least for a span of seven years or according to the company policies. It should be retrievable any time it is required. Therefore, organizing minutes of meetings in well-designed filing system is essential.

- If your minutes incorporated a document by reference, attach the document.
- You should also discard any drafts of your minutes including the electronic versions after the final version has been adopted.

(Source: WikiHow: How to write Corporate Minutes)

Post reading tasks:

1. Answer the following in about 30 words each:
 - a. Define ‘minutes of a meeting’
 - b. Enumerate the points to make the minutes reliable and trustworthy.
 - c. Write the structure of the minutes.
 - d. What are the decisions arrived in the meeting of Rainbow mall?
 - e. Bring out the necessities of writing corporate minutes.
2. Describe the methods to write effective corporate minutes. (in 200words)
3. Imagine yourself as an assistant manager of your company and prepare the minutes of a meeting recently held in your office. (in 200words)

WRITING SKILLS

1. Writing an Introduction for an academic essay

Pre-text task-	Vocabulary
<i>trivial</i>	<i>foresee</i>
<i>humorous</i>	<i>appraise</i>
<i>philosophically</i>	<i>consistency</i>
<i>jargons</i>	<i>over-burdened</i>
<i>cliché</i>	<i>reiterate</i>

Essays can be written on any topic, serious or trivial, concrete, or abstract. The tone and style also may be humorous, ironic, or factual. While writing an essay, it is essential to understand the meaning and scope of the topic. Begin the essay with an appropriate introductory paragraph, introduce the main theme of the essay and indicate its scope. It is always good to begin any piece of writing with a definition or an interesting and relevant anecdote. One should avoid introductions that plunge into the discussion right in the beginning itself. The writer should be scrupulous to avoid long, irrelevant, flashy, or abstruse introduction. Therefore, while writing the introductory part of the essay, certain points may be adopted to make it comprehensible and lucid.

Tips for writing effective introduction

1. Keep your introduction brief and effective.
2. Avoid starting abruptly or too philosophically.
3. Define or explain the title in a precise, specific way.
4. Use quotations, dictionary meanings, statements, or sayings to introduce the reader to the main idea.
5. Don't take sides on an issue or sound prejudiced in your approach.
6. Avoid jargons, clichés, and bombastic beginnings.
7. Don't present enigmatic ideas in the beginning itself.
8. Use simple language with concrete thoughts.

A good introduction

- Catches the reader's attention and gets the reader interested in what is going to follow.
- Makes the reader know what the general topic of the writing is
- Tells the reader specifically what the main idea of the writing is.

Writing an introduction for an academic essay:

- An introductory paragraph of an essay of your subject can be especially problematic for those students who rely on theoretical knowledge instead of putting their practical thinking to test. For example, the study of management needs practical skill, and so, an introduction for management essay cannot be based on pure theory. Even when the problem is quickly introduced, one needs to highlight the practical meaning of the questions in discussion. Creative thinking skills are essential to start the essay.
- After you've managed to hook the reader with the practical relevance of your subject, you can continue to a summary of the problem you plan to discuss followed by a full overview of the aspects you are going to analyze.
- Finally, you are to proceed to a thesis statement, which is — basically — the main argument of your entire paper. You are going to discuss it in greater detail in the main body of your management essay.

When writing an introduction, you should typically use a 'general to specific' structure. That is, introduce the problem or topic the essay will address in a general sense to provide context, before narrowing down to your position and line of argument.

Structure of an essay

(Image Source: Writing Essay.jpg-wikimedia commons)

The introduction of an essay must be substantial. It should stimulate an interest in the reader to anticipate the content of the rest of the paper such as the paragraphs that follow and the conclusion.

This will be possible only when the introduction presented is clear in the theme and concept and prepare the reader for the facts which will follow.

To give a good introduction you must revise your writing many times. First drafts that can't be improved in some way by editing and reviewing are rare to nonexistent. The first draft should be followed by reviewing and revising. This will entail checking grammar, spelling, and punctuation. You should ensure that the writing style is simple, precise, and concise. Remove irrelevant information or sentences. Check if ideas are repeated. If any part of the sentence is ambiguous rewrite it. The first part of an essay is very important as it not only sets the tone for the essay, but it also will aim at sustaining the reader's interest. Much work must be done in this part.

2. Paraphrasing an academic essay

Just like the introduction of an essay, the summarizing or paraphrasing of an essay is also vital. Sometime, improper paraphrasing may mar the entire essay. While a summary will give a general idea of the essay a paraphrase will add more details. Though paraphrasing occurs at the end of an essay, it should be constructive and impressive

Tips for developing a good paraphrasing:

- While paraphrasing, you are supposed to reinforce the ideas already established in the main body of your essay. So, inclusion of any new idea or thought should be avoided.
- Concluding points or ideas should be forceful and dynamic.
- Don't elaborate on a single point of an essay alone; rather cover up all the ideas illustrated in the entire paragraphs.
- The paraphrase should comply with the discussion found in the body of the essay.
- Concluding sentences should be optimistic and agile.
- Paraphrasing paragraph should be crisp, short, and provoke inquisitiveness in reader to probe deep into the subject.
- It is always good if you give your own ideas at the end instead of citing quotations from other sources.
- Conclude the essay with proper convincing statements and don't leave abrupt statements.

Develop an understanding of the original text. Read the paragraphs that you need to summarize several times. Get a complete understanding of the ideas in it. Identify words that are difficult and find out the meaning. Thus, you will be able to use the most accurate words when you summarize.

Change the original word choice. One rule of paraphrasing is to write in your own words. Here is where you need to explore your unique style in writing.

There are several ways to paraphrase. Since each writer has her/his own unique style therefore there is no one right way to paraphrase.

The introductory paragraph and the paraphrased paragraph too should reiterate the main points. The force with which you express the concluding ideas are especially important, because the merit and credit of your complete essay solely depends on the way it is paraphrased. For a good essay, the concluding part should include suggestion or call for action, prediction (positive or negative outcome) and a question. Try to provide innovative statements in the concluding paragraph, so that the readers may be inspired to take up further studies in that specific area. By all these methods, you can make your essay more comprehensible, focused, and forceful.

Read the following sample essay:

(Source: Dr. Saravanadevi R. Associate professor & Head, Dept of Management, GAC, Kumarapalyam, Erode, Tamil Nadu)

POTENTIAL APPRAISAL

Business organizations always aim at placing right people in the right place at the right time. This can be achieved by potential appraisal or evaluation. Through a potential appraisal, unutilized ability may be identified. It is the latent capacity and qualities that is found in a person when a person is at work.

The objectives of potential evaluation are to promote an employee to higher levels of jobs involving higher order or responsibilities. The employee can effectively discharge these tasks without being over-burdened and stretched. It also assists the organization to allocate jobs among employees as per their capabilities so that organizational responsibilities are discharged effectively. Through its foresight into the future, it can enable the individual and the organization to grow. Potential appraisal and performance appraisal must go hand in hand. It is also an important tool for Human Resource Management.

Potential appraisal is used in several human resource management functions such as human resource planning, career planning, succession planning, promotion/ termination, decisions and employee training and development.

In this context, potential means a prospective employee who is capable to undertake different challenging assignments. Potential of employees need to be discovered for organizational effectiveness. Organizations must aim to utilize the full potential of the workforce, institute an environment to unleash the latent creativity, create conditions promoting innovation and team working, and so forth. This also helps in identifying potential leaders in an organization.

(Image source: Project management planning – Free photo on Pixabay)

A potential employee is characterized by the following attributes:

1. Ability to foresee future opportunities.
2. Consistency in approach and performance.
3. Responsive to conditions whatever come in the way.
4. Person with high level of integrity.
5. Broader vision and micro perception.

Once the potential evaluation is made it is easy to place the employees in any of the following classes:

1. **Low Potential – Low Performance.** These employees are low on both dimensions. They should be nurtured to improve their levels.
2. **High Potential – Low Performance.** They are given new opportunities in new department or in a new location. Failure to perform will incur reclassification and planned separation.
3. **Low Potential – High Performance.** They called solid citizens. They are encouraged to do well in the current positions.
4. **High Potential – High Performance.** They are the stars of the team. They are given more opportunities related to development.

However, it is the prime duty of Human Resource Manager to appraise the hidden talents and potentials of every employee and identify the potential class that each employee fits in.

In this manner the right talent will be utilized for the right purpose.

Post –reading task 1

Say whether the following statements are true or false:

1. Any writing will be good if it begins with a definition or an anecdote.
2. An introduction of an essay should belong.
3. An introduction should not reveal the main ideas of the upcoming passages.
4. For management students, pure theoretical knowledge is not enough to deal with their problem of study.
5. To give a good introduction, revising the written item is essential.
6. Paraphrasing means conveying different messages.
7. You should not include any new ideas in paraphrase.
8. You need not understand the original text to paraphrase.
9. The merit and credit of the entire essay depends on the way it is paraphrased.
10. The paraphrase should be brief and forceful.

Task 2

“The spread of e-commerce during this pandemic period is faster than the spread of the virus”- Write an essay providing a proper introduction and a paraphrase in about 200 words.

WRITING SKILLS

Punctuation and Capitalization

<https://www.teachstarter.com/au/blog/26-punctuation-resources-activities/>

Punctuation

The system of signs or symbols, such as full stop, comma, and exclamatory mark, used in written language is called Punctuation. Punctuation marks show a reader how a sentence is constructed and how it should be read. Every sentence should include a capital letter at the start, and a punctuation mark at the end.

Why Punctuation matters?

Life would be confusing without proper punctuation.

Look at these sentences

1. some people find inspiration in cooking their families and dogs

Vs.

Some people find inspiration in cooking, their families and dogs.

2. lets eat grandpa

Vs

“Let’s eat, Grandpa!”

The sentences convey *totally* different things as per the proper usage of punctuations.

For the sake of family members and Grandpa’s life, use proper punctuation. Punctuation saves lives and keeps people alive!

3. Now, this is a big one. Consider the following sentences. Note how the meaning changes drastically when the position of the comma changes.

a woman without her man is nothing

“A woman, without her man, is nothing.” (A woman’s success is because of a man)

Now, let’s change up where we’re placing the punctuation:

“A woman: without her, man is nothing.” (A man’s success is because of a woman)

Here is an infographic on various punctuations used in English

PUNCTUATION MARK

Full Stop

Used at the end of a sentence

Question Mark

Used at the end of an interrogative sentence to form a question.

Comma

Used to denote a pause in a sentence

Exclamation Mark

Used to denote shock, surprise, anger or a raised voice.

Quotation Mark

Used to show that someone else has said it

Colon

Used to indicate what is to follow next.

Semi Colon

Used to link two independent clauses.

Apostrophe

Used to show possession or for contraction of word.

Hyphen

Used to glue words together.

Slash

Used to separate letters, numbers or words.

Ellipsis Mark

Used to separate items in a series.

Round Brackets

Used to add extra information in a sentence.

www.eslgrammar.org

CAPITALIZATION

Capitalization is one of the most basic and important elements of writing. Capitalization draws the reader's attention to names, titles, and more. Capitalization also marks the start of new sentences and new paragraphs, provides signals to the reader, and helps to create a structure and a hierarchy in written language.

Basic Capitalization Rules

1. Capitalize proper nouns.

- To indicate the names of people, such as Vijay, David, or Anwar.
- To denote the names of months and days, such as January, August, Sunday, Thursday
- To denote days of national/international importance, such as Independence Day, Women's Day

- Finally, proper nouns also include the names of buildings, landmarks, and companies, such as the Leaning Tower of Pisa, the Statue of Liberty, or Verizon
2. **Use capitalization with proper adjectives.**
 - Indian, American, Italian, German
 3. **Capitalize titles of works.**
 - A Tale of Two Cities, Titanic, Ode To A Nightingale, Beats
 4. **Use a capital at the beginning of a sentence.** The first word of every sentence should be capitalized, regardless of what kind of word.
 5. **Capitalize the first word of a full sentence in a quotation.** Sentences appearing within quotes also should have a capital letter in the beginning.
She said to me “Do you feel alright?”
 6. **Use capitalization when referring to a period or an event.**
 - The Chola Period.
 7. **Capitalization with the pronoun “I.”** One of the most notable words to make sure to capitalize is the pronoun “I.” I refer to oneself. This is a unique and specific usage.
 8. **Capitalize family relationships.**
 - Aunt Preethi" or "Cousin Ajith."
 9. **Capitalize people’s titles.**
 - Mr. Ms. Miss, and Dr.

Remember these punctuation rules while writing:

PUNCTUATION RULES

ENGLISH
PUNCTUATION

RULE 1

Every sentence must end with a full stop.

Proper nouns (names of people, places, brands, etc, i.e. unique instances of a class) must always be capitalised.

RULE 2

RULE 3

When you use opening quotation marks, do not forget to use closing quotation marks at the end of the quoted word or phrase.

Quotation marks are when quoting or sometimes to convey irony, not for emphasis; emphasis is conveyed by boldening or italicisation, followed by an exclamation mark.

RULE 4

RULE 5

Do not use an apostrophe when you are pluralising a word. The plural of toy is toys, not toy's. Apostrophes are used to form contractions (it is = it's) and indicate possession.

The ellipsis, used to indicate variously the intentional omission of a section of text, an unfinished thought, and a trailing off into silence, consists of only 3 dots. It is pointless to add more dots to an ellipsis

RULE 6

RULE 7

As per the rules of British English, any punctuation mark that is not part of a quoted section of text must be placed outside the quotation marks.

Do not link independent clauses with commas. Independent clauses are groupings of words that can stand alone as sentences.

RULE 8

RULE 9

Use a comma after the introductory element of a sentence. The introductory element is a word or a phrase that begins a sentence by providing background, or simply modifies it.

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Activity 1

Analyse the Story given below and list down the various punctuations mentioned in

the story and write their definition.

E.g.

1. **Comma** – Used for pausing; took its place between words; without the break commas provide,

words run amok, becoming jumbled, unwieldy, and confusing; a well-placed comma can change the meaning of a sentence.

The Day Punctuation Came to Town

Written by Kimberlee Gard | Illustrated by Sandie Sonke

The Punctuations had just moved to Alphabet City and the kids—Exclamation Point, Question Mark, Period, and Comma—were excited about their first day of school. Exclamation Point was in a rush to get there. “We are going to have so much fun!” he said. He “was always excited about something.” Question Mark was a little more subdued. She wondered if the other kids would be nice and even pondered whether they were walking in the right direction. “Comma kept pausing,” and Period said she would let her siblings know when to stop.

When they got to school and introduced themselves, the student letters were confused. They’d never seen anyone like the Punctuations before. As the letters practiced forming words, Exclamation Point joined W, O, and W; Question Mark helped out W, H, and O; and “Period brought each sentence to a tidy end.” For Comma, though, it wasn’t so easy. As he tried to squeeze in between letters, he began to feel as if he was just a bother. Undetected, he tiptoed away.

Meanwhile, in the classroom, Exclamation Point had all the letters scrambling to make more and more exciting words. There was a lot of cheering and booming, ducking, and running. Question Mark asked if maybe they shouldn't all quiet down a bit, but no one was listening. Even Period couldn't get them to stop. Pretty soon, there was a huge word pileup. In the next moment it came crashing down and all the letters "tumbled through the door, spilling into the hall." There, they found Comma, who just stared in disbelief. His siblings wondered why he was in the hall instead of in the classroom. Comma told them how he felt. But, "Comma, without you, things become a disaster!" Exclamation Point said. Period and Question Mark agreed.

Then his siblings gently reminded little Comma about how each member of their family has a certain purpose. They told him, "we all work together to help letters and the words they make." Once everyone had gone back into the classroom, the letters continued making words. But now Comma took his place between them. When the letters looked confused, he explained that it was his job to keep order and that words and punctuation needed each other to make good and clear sentences.

For children just learning about sentence structure and how punctuation and words fit together to create meaning, Kimberlee Gard's lively story helps them visualize and understand the different roles of each punctuation mark. Coming at the end of a sentence and accompanied by vocal clues, exclamation points, question marks, and periods are more familiar to kids. But what about that comma, which seems to float around here and there? Gard demonstrates that without the break commas provide, words run amok, becoming jumbled, unwieldy, and confusing. Readers will respond to the classroom setting, where the letters work and play together during lessons, and they will be eager to make friends with the Punctuation family themselves.

If any readers think learning about punctuation is dry and dull, Sandie Sonke's vibrant colors and cartoon characters will change their minds. The Punctuations (and their butterfly friend Apostrophe) is sweet and earnest, wanting to fit into the class and make a difference. As the letters form words, the purple Punctuations are easy for kids to pick out, allowing for discussion of their distinct roles. The tangled piles of letters invite kids to make words from the muddle. After Comma realizes his importance and the letters embrace him, the story ends with a familiar and funny example of just how a well-placed comma can change the meaning of a sentence.

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<https://celebratepicturebooks.com/tag/writing-resources-for-kids/>

Activity 2

Explore the following websites and complete the Punctuation Marks Graphic Organizer.

Punctuation Tree: <http://guidetogrammar.org/grammar/marks/marks.htm>

English Club: <https://www.englishclub.com/writing/punctuation.htm>

Grammar Book: https://www.grammarbook.com/english_rules.asp

Punctuation Marks Graphic Organizer

Write the rules for using each of the punctuation marks below. Each row represents a different rule. In the right-hand column, provide an example of the rule in use.

Symbol (!?, etc.)	Punctuation Name	Rule	Example of Rule in Use